

Development of an Automated Catheter Production Line with SCADA Integration for the Medical Device Industry

by

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A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment
of the requirements for the
Degree of Bachelor of Engineering with Honours
in AUTOMATION AND ROBOTICS

TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY OF THE SHANNON

31/03/2025

Abstract

Manual assembly of medical catheters is common in the healthcare industry but remains inefficient, error-prone and difficult to scale. These challenges highlight the need for advanced automation to enhance precision, throughput, and regulatory compliance in catheter manufacturing. This dissertation presents a comprehensive solution that integrates robotic arms with custom end of arm tooling (EOAT), vision systems and real time feedback mechanisms to automate critical stages of catheter production.

Digital twin simulations developed in RoboDK enabled optimisation of workflows, collision detection and offline programming. The use of force and torque feedback via the UR5e's built in sensors, allowed safe handling of delicate components. Vision systems, configured using Cognex In-Sight tools and AI based inspection, ensured a reliable defect detection and quality control throughout the process.

A SCADA-style monitoring layer was implemented using Siemens WinCC and Power BI, supporting real time data visibility, alarm handling and traceability. Material selection, mechanical design in SolidWorks and PLC control via Siemens TIA Portal ensured compliance with ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 11 standards. Lean and Six Sigma principles were also considered to minimise waste and improve process capability.

This project demonstrates how automation and simulation technologies can replace manual catheter assembly with a scalable, precise and regulatory complaint system meeting the growing demands of the medical device industry.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor, Patrick Doran, for his help, motivation and support throughout the year, which made this project possible. I'm also grateful to my lecturers, whose courses played a big part in shaping this work. A special thanks to the staff at the TUS engineering for their helpful advice and cooperation.

Lastly, I would like to thank the Operational Excellence (OpEx) team at a leading medical device company in the Midlands region of Ireland. Although this project was not carried out in direct collaboration with the company, the knowledge, experience and insights I gained during my third-year work placement had a significant impact on the direction and development of this dissertation.

As a certified Yellow Belt in Lean Six Sigma, I applied the principals of process optimisation and quality improvement learned during my time there, which played an important role in shaping the projects approach and execution.

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Nomenclature

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CBE	Control Board Extension (used in SIMATIC DC Master CBE20)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DC	Direct Current
EOAT	End-of-Arm Tooling
EtO	Ethylene Oxide
FAT	Factory Acceptance Test
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GAMP 5	Good Automated Manufacturing Practice Version 5
GEP	Good Engineering Practice
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practice
GSD	General Station Description
GSDML	General Station Description Markup Language
GxP	Good Practice (x = variable depending on the specific field)
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HPV	Hydrogen Peroxide Vapour
IED	Industrial Emissions Directive
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IQ	Installation Qualification
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
Nm	Newton-Metre (unit of torque)
OEE	Overall Equipment Effectiveness
OQ	Operational Qualification
PAT	Process Analytical Technology
PDF	Portable Document Format

PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PN/DP	Profinet/Distributed Peripherals (used in S7-1500 CPUs)
Profinet	Process Field Net – Industrial Ethernet Protocol
PQ	Performance Qualification
QMS	Quality Management System
QR Code	Quick Response Code
RoboDK	Robotics Simulation and Offline Programming Software
ROS	Robot Operating System
ROI	Return on Investment
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SCARA	Selective Compliance Assembly Robot Arm
SLS	Safety Limit Switch
STL	Stereolithography File
SnAPP	Smart Algorithm for Part Presence (Cognex AI tool)
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TCP	Tool Centre Point
TIA	Totally Integrated Automation
UR5e	Universal Robots Collaborative Robot Model
UDI	Unique Device Identification
URP	Universal Robots Program File
UV	Ultraviolet
WEEE	Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WinCC	Windows Control Centre (Siemens SCADA Software)

1. Introduction

The manufacturing of medical catheters is a vital part of modern healthcare, enabling minimally invasive procedures that improve patient outcomes. However, much of the production still relies on manual assembly, which can lead to inefficiencies, human error and difficulties in scaling. These issues are becoming more urgent due to rising global demand, driven by an ageing population and increasing rates of chronic illness.

While automation has transformed industries like automotive and electronics, its adoption in catheter manufacturing has been slower, mainly due to the delicate materials involved and strict regulatory requirements. Nonetheless, automation offers clear advantages in this sector enhancing precision, reducing defect rates and improving compliance with standards such as ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 11.

This dissertation presents the design and simulation of an automated catheter production line. The system integrates digital twin modelling using RoboDK, PLC control via Siemens TIA Portal, machine vision inspection with Cognex, and SCADA-style monitoring through Power BI. MATLAB is also used to estimate mechanical forces, such as torque during cutting operations, while validating the system's mechanical assumptions in the absence of live hardware.

The aim is to demonstrate how simulation-based automation can improve production efficiency, traceability, and regulatory compliance. By combining robotics, vision systems, control logic and real-time data analysis in a modular framework, the project provides a scalable model for the medical device industry.

The structure of this dissertation is as follows:

- Chapter 2 revises the literature on catheter manufacturing, automation technologies, and compliance.
- Chapter 3 outlines the methodology used to develop and simulate the automated system.
- Chapter 4 details the implementation of each subsystem, including CAD modelling and integration strategies.
- Chapter 5 presents simulation results and performance evaluations, including MATLAB torque calculations.
- Chapter 6 discusses the benefits, limitations and industry relevance of the system.
- Chapter 7 concludes the work and outlines opportunities for future development.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to Automation in Medical Devices

Automation has become a fundamental aspect of modern manufacturing, particularly in industries requiring high precision, efficiency, and regulatory compliance. In medical device manufacturing, automation minimises manual errors, increases throughput, and ensures consistent product quality (R. Kumar and J. Lee 2021). With the rising demand for high-quality medical devices, manufacturers are increasingly integrating robotics, machine vision, and artificial intelligence (AI) to meet production standards and regulatory requirements (U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) 2023).

2.1.1 Overview of Catheter Medical Devices

Catheter medical devices are essential in modern healthcare, used for procedures such as fluid drainage, medication delivery, and minimally invasive surgeries. These devices must meet strict biocompatibility, flexibility, and durability standards to ensure patient safety. Medtronic is a key manufacturer of high-precision catheters, particularly for neurovascular and cardiovascular applications. Their products, such as the Torq™ Diagnostic Catheter, used in cardiovascular procedures, highlight the advancements in catheter technology, particularly in achieving precision, flexibility and control during diagnostic interventions.

Figure 2.1, Torq™ Diagnostic Catheter, (Medtronic 2024)

Catheter manufacturing must comply with strict regulatory standards such as ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 820 to ensure product quality and safety. Automation is essential for improving precision and consistency. Medtronic leverages Industry 4.0 technologies, including digital twins, adaptive robotics, and AI-driven inspection systems, to optimise and scale its catheter production processes (Medtronic 2023).

2.1.2 Background and Evolution of Automation in Medical Device Manufacturing

The automation of medical device manufacturing gained momentum in the late 20th century, initially focusing on improving consistency and precision in the production of critical healthcare components. Early automation efforts primarily targeted high-volume processes such as injection moulding for syringes, drug delivery systems, and diagnostic consumables (Smith *et al.* 2019). The primary motivation for these advancements was economic aiming to reduce production costs, improve product reliability, and meet the growing global demand for high-quality medical devices (Y. Zhang *et al.* 2022).

Figure 2.2, Medical Device Manufacturing 1973, Progressiveautomations.com

As technology evolved, automation in medical manufacturing expanded beyond simple repetitive tasks. By the early 2000s, robotic systems began to be used in intricate assembly processes, including suturing, catheter handling, and endoscopic instrument manufacturing (Van den Berg, Fischer, *et al.* 2020). Advances in machine vision, force feedback control, and precision robotics enabled more complex automation solutions capable of performing delicate tasks with high accuracy (Rahman, M. A, *et al.* 2021).

However, recent innovations in robotics, artificial intelligence and digital twin technologies have reignited interest in catheter automation. These technologies allow for virtual modelling, real time process optimisation, and intelligent error correction, making the automation of complex assemblies increasingly viable (F. Tao *et al.* 2019). The current project builds on this evolution by simulating an integrated catheter manufacturing system that incorporates robotic control, PLC logic, machine vision, and SCADA visualisation, demonstrating a modern, scalable approach to medical device production.

2.1.3 Current and Future Trends in Automated Catheter Manufacturing

Modern catheter manufacturing is being reshaped by the integration of robotics. Emerging technologies such as robot-assisted assembly, real-time quality control using vision systems, and intelligent process monitoring through SCADA and IoT solutions are paving the way for fully automated production lines (Gao 2022). These innovations aim to reduce dependence on manual labour, enhance production rates, and ensure strict adherence to ISO 13485, FDA 21 CFR Part 11, and Good Automated Manufacturing Practice (GAMP 5) standards (European Medicines Agency (EMA) 2025).

Figure 2.3, SCADA incorporating the PLC, HMI, UR5e, conveyor, Cognex Camera, and Power BI used in this project. MS Visio

Figure 2.3 illustrates the architecture of the automated catheter manufacturing system developed in this project. The diagram shows the integration between key components: the Siemens PLC, UR5e robot for material handling, Cognex vision system for defect detection, HMI for operator interaction, and Power BI for production visualisation. This connected system enables monitoring, coordinated control, and traceable performance analytics, reflecting current trends in Industry 4.0 enabled medical device manufacturing.

2.2 Automation in Catheter Assembly

The transition from manual to automated catheter assembly represents a major step forward in improving production efficiency, precision and compliance with medical device regulations. Traditional manual methods, while effective for small-scale production, present challenges in process variability, labour costs, and quality control. By integrating automation technologies such as robotic handling, PLC-controlled welding, force sensing, and vision inspection, manufacturers can achieve higher throughput, reduced defect rates, and enhanced traceability (Y. Zhang *et al.* 2023).

Figure 2.4 presents a flowchart of the catheter manufacturing workflow, outlining the sequential material handling stages from raw material intake to final product release. Key stages include raw material handling, cutting and preparation, bonding and assembly, quality inspection, functional testing, sterilisation and final packaging. This visual representation reflects the structured, regulated nature of medical device production and highlights the points at which automation technologies can optimise consistency, traceability and throughput.

Figure 2.4, Flowchart of Catheter Manufacturing and Material Handling Process, MS Visio

2.2.1 Robotic Handling and Assembly in Catheter Manufacturing

The integration of industrial robotics such as FANUC, ABB and Universal Robots (UR) enables precise positioning and handling of catheter components during assembly. In this project a Universal Robots UR5e collaborative robot was used to simulate automated handling of catheter components, including tube placement, cutting station loading and final packaging.

Compared to traditional six-axis robots such as FANUC or ABB IRB series, the UR5e offers a more adaptable and compact platform ideal for flexible, semi-automated assembly lines. Its intuitive compatibility with grippers such as the Robotiq Hand-E, makes it ideal for soft materials like catheter tubing. The UR5e's repeatability and integrated force/torque feedback make it especially effective in precision tasks such as guidewire insertion, bonding alignment and automated transfer between stations (Rahman, M. A., *et al.* 2021).

The use of RoboDK as a digital twin environment allows the UR5e's path planning and motion sequences to be tested virtually before implementation, reducing programming time and ensuring safe, collision free operation. A simulation can allow the robot to interact with a digital cutting station, conveyor system and packaging area to demonstrate the potential for a fully integrated robotic workflow. This level of automation can significantly improve production output and reduce operator fatigue, while also enabling enhanced process control and traceability which is critical for compliance with ISO 13485 and GAMP 5 standards in medical device manufacturing.

Figure 2.4, UR5e, Universal Robots

By replacing manual handling with robotic motion, the system improves assembly accuracy, reduces variability and enhances output in regulated medical device manufacturing (Gao *et al.* 2022). This transition has proven particularly valuable in catheter production, where even minor inconsistencies in tube positioning or bonding pressure have led to product defects or regulatory non-compliance. Robotic systems such as the UR5e have provided consistent, repeatable motion under tightly controlled parameters. This shift has not only minimised the risk of human error and operator fatigue but has also enabled continuous operation with reduced downtime. Automation has supported greater standardisation across production, improving traceability and quality assurance which are both essential in meeting ISO and FDA requirements.

2.2.2 PLC and SCADA Integration for Welding and Force Sensing

In medical device manufacturing, Siemens PLCs have been widely adopted for managing automated processes such as welding, force sensing, and robotic sequencing. In particular, the S7-1500 series, including the CPU 1516-3 PN/DP, has provided high speed processing and robust real time communication capabilities suitable for precision critical applications like catheter assembly. Siemens' Totally Integrated Automation (TIA) Portal has offered a unified platform for programming, monitoring and controlling components including robots, conveyors and vision systems.

Figure 2.5, Siemens SIMATIC S7-1500 Series, RS

Programmable logic controllers have been used to regulate key welding parameters such as temperature, pressure and bonding time, ensuring strong, consistent joins between catheter components. Real time integration of force and torque feedback has allowed robotic arms to adjust handling pressure dynamically, reducing the risk of material damage during insertion and bonding. In parallel, the WinCC SCADA system has enabled real-time visualisation, alarm handling and process data logging, supporting both traceability and regulatory compliance in according with ISO 13485 and GAMP 5 standards (Smith and Taylor 2019).

To enable seamless coordination between system components, communication protocols such as Profinet have been frequently implemented to connect Siemens PLCs with robots, HMIs, vision systems and SCADA platforms (M. Raj *et al.* 2021). Profinet has allowed for high-speed data exchange, which is essential in time sensitive operations like robotic welding or vision-based quality inspection. Research has also highlighted scalability of PLC based architecture in medical device manufacturing, where modular control logic enables quick adaptation to different catheter types, production volumes or process variations.

2.2.3 Vision Inspection for Quality Assurance

Automated vision inspection systems have been widely adopted in medical device manufacturing to ensure product quality and consistency. Systems such as the Cognex In-Sight 3800, designed for high-speed, high-resolution inspection, have been used in industry to verify critical aspects of catheter assembly. These include dimensional accuracy, component positioning and detection of surface defects such as crack, contamination, or material misalignment (Van den Berg, L., *et al.* 2020).

Figure 2.6, Cognex 3800, AI Based Vision System Sensor

2.2.4 Force and Torque Sensors in Assembly Processes

To ensure precision and consistency in bonding, insertion and tube welding, force and torque sensors regulate key process parameters. These sensors ensure that correct insertion forces are applied when connecting catheter components, prevent excessive pressure during bonding to reduce defects, and enable adaptive process control by dynamically adjusting forces based on real-time feedback (Muller 2018).

Figure 2.7, Force and Torque Sensor, UR

2.2.5 Robotics Welding and Laser Bonding for Tube End Connectors

The bonding of catheter tube connectors has been recognised as a precision critical stage in the manufacturing process where material compatibility and joint integrity are essential. Robotic laser welding and thermal bonding techniques have offered non-contact, controlled energy application minimising the risk of heat related material degradation. These technologies have provided uniform heat distribution, allowing for consistent sealing and greater repeatability compared to manual binding or heat-sealing methods (R. Kumar and J. Lee 2021).

Figure 2.8, illustrates a RoboDK simulated material handling cell relevant to this process, demonstrating robotic coordination

Recent studies have demonstrated that the integration of AI-driven process monitoring during robotic welding can significantly improve defect detection, reduce scrap rates, and lower rework costs. Real time feedback from temperature or force sensors has enabled dynamic process adjustments, enhancing bonding reliability. The shift toward robotic bonding and automated inspection has contributed to a higher output and more consistent product quality.

2.3 Industrial IOT and Smart Manufacturing in Medical Devices

The adoption of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and smart manufacturing principles is transforming medical device production, including catheter assembly, by enabling real time monitoring, predictive maintenance and data driven decision making. The combination of IoT-enabled sensors, AI based analytics, and cloud-based platforms has allowed for continuous optimisation of manufacturing workflows and early detection of process deviations (A. Choudhury 2021).

These smart systems have also improved traceability and regulatory compliance under frameworks such as ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 820, offering automated reporting and digital documentation. As shown in Figure 2.9, IIoT applications in catheter manufacturing operate within a cycle of real-time data acquisition, privacy and security management, and AI enhanced learning, supporting long term performance.

Figure 2.9, Cycle of IIoT Applications in Smart Medical Device Manufacturing. MS Visio

Recent developments in IIoT have also emphasised the importance of data security and system interoperability, particularly in regulated industries such as medical devices. Ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of production data is essential for maintaining compliance with FDA and EU MDR requirements. Cloud platforms such as Siemens MindSphere and Power BI have been employed in industry to securely collect and analyse data from PLCs, robots and vision systems.

2.3.1 IoT-Enabled Sensors for Real-Time Monitoring of Catheter Assembly

IoT-enabled sensors have been widely adopted in catheter manufacturing to monitor real time process variables and maintain product integrity. Force and torque sensors detect insertion pressures to prevent damage during bonding, while temperature and humidity sensors maintain optimal conditions for curing and welding. Vibration and pressure sensors track robotic joints and welding stations, enabling early fault detection (A. Choudhury 2021). Data from these sensors is transmitted to a Manufacturing Execution System (MES) or cloud platforms such as Siemens MindSphere or Power BI, allowing predictive maintenance across the production cycle.

Figure 2.10, illustrates a fully integrated smart manufacturing cycle, highlighting the interaction between automation systems, IoT, digital twins, SCADA, and cloud-based analytics. MS Visio

2.3.2 Data Logging and Predictive Maintenance in Catheter Production

Predictive maintenance is a key advantage of IIOT in catheter manufacturing, significantly reducing unexpected downtime and maintenance costs. Continuous equipment health monitoring is achieved through IoT sensors that track motor performance, welding temperature, and conveyor belt speeds, detecting deviations that may indicate potential failures. AI-based failure prediction utilises machine learning models to analyse historical sensor data, predicting when robotic systems or welding stations require maintenance, allowing for proactive repairs before breakdowns occur (Y. Zhang *et al.* 2023).

Cloud based data logging further enhances traceability by integrating SCADA-enabled IoT systems that record sensor readings, machine performance, and production batch data (M. Raj *et al.* 2021). This digital traceability supports regulatory compliance and improves process transparency. By implementing predictive maintenance strategies, manufacturers have been able to extend equipment lifespan, improve resource efficiency, and minimise costly disruptions in catheter production line (P. Ghosh and C. Lin 2020).

2.3.3 Industry 4.0 and Smart Factory Concept in Medical device Production

The emergence of Industry 4.0 has introduced transformative technologies to the medical device sector, enabling the creation of smart factories through the convergence of cyber physical systems, AI driven automation, and real time data connectivity. These advancements have been increasingly applied to catheter production, where precision, traceability and consistency are critical.

Digital twins are virtual models of the production environment. They have been used to simulate catheter assembly processes in real time, allowing engineers to identify bottlenecks and optimise robotic workflows before physical deployment (Bai and Zhou 2022). When paired with live data from IoT-enabled sensors, digital twins can dynamically reflect the current state of production and predict system performance under various conditions.

AI-powered quality control systems, such as those using Cognex vision technology, have leveraged deep learning algorithms to inspect catheters for subtle defects including microcracks, surface contamination, and misalignment of bonded components (R. Kumar and J. Lee 2021).

AI driven analytics have enabled autonomous adjustment of key parameters such as robotic speed bonding force and defect rejection thresholds minimising human intervention and reducing process variability. When combined with Industrial IoT (IIoT), SCADA platforms, and cloud-based analytics, smart manufacturing environments allow catheter production facilities to significantly improve operational efficiency, maintain regulatory compliance and meet growing global demand for high precision medical devices.

Figure 2.11, Digital Twin Framework, MS Visio

Figure 2.11 illustrates the digital twin framework applied to catheter manufacturing, showing the interaction between the physical industrial robot and its virtual counterpart.

2.3.4 Cybersecurity and Regulatory Reporting

As catheter production increasingly relies on digital automation, cybersecurity and regulatory reporting is critical. The implementation of secure, encrypted data storage solutions ensures adherence to the FDA and ISO 27001 cybersecurity standards (ISO 27001 2018). Automated reporting tools within SCADA and Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) enable real-time data logging and simplify compliance with EPA and FDA regulatory audits.

Automated reporting functions integrated into SCADA platforms and MES have enabled continuous data logging, system validation, and audit trail generation. This level of live documentation simplifies regulatory inspections by agencies such as the EPA and FDA, ensuring traceability, process transparency and rapid response in the event of deviations (ISPE 2021).

2.4 Digital Twin Technology in Medical Device Manufacturing

The adoption of digital twin technology in medical device manufacturing is revolutionising process simulation, robotics integration, and predictive maintenance. A digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical manufacturing systems, allowing engineers to simulate production scenarios, optimise efficiency, and reduce errors before deployment (Schleipen and Jasperneite 2021). In catheter assembly, digital twins play a crucial role in robotics handling, PLC coordination, and vision-guided quality control, enduring seamless automation and regulatory compliance.

In catheter assembly, digital twins play a pivotal role in simulating robotic handling, PLC logic and vision guided quality inspection, ensuring that all automation subsystems operate in synchronisation. These simulations allow manufacturers to validate motion paths, optimise cycle times, and test control strategies under virtual conditions. This minimises risk associated with manual commissioning and physical prototyping (Raj 2022).

2.4.1 Digital Twin Technology for Process Simulation

Digital twins' technology has enabled manufacturers to simulate and optimise catheter production processes in a virtual environment before physical implementation. In the context of robotic assembly cells, welding operations and material handling stations, digital twins replicate real time conditions using kinematic modelling, control logic and sensor input to evaluate system performance. This allows engineers to detect inefficiencies, optimise motion paths and identify potential collisions or bottlenecks prior to deployment, significantly reducing development time and operational costs (Schleipen and Jasperneite 2021).

Simulation platforms such as RoboDK have been used to model UR5e robotic workflows for catheter positioning and tube cutting, validating task sequences and reachability within a virtual cell. These simulations mirror the robot's real-world parameters, including payload, joint limits and tool centre point (TCP) calibrations. When combined with live PLC logic and force sensor feedback, the digital twin provides a powerful tool for predictive validation and continuous process improvement.

Figure 2.12 presents a side-by-side comparison between the simulated UR5e model in RoboDK and the physical robot setup, demonstrating the alignment between virtual planning and real-world execution. This comparison demonstrates the high level of accuracy achievable through digital twin modelling, highlighting how virtual planning tools can replicate real world motion, end effector positioning and task sequencing. By validating workflows in a simulated environment before deployment, engineers can reduce trial and error during integration, improve cycle time estimation and ensure alignment between design intent and actual system behaviour.

Figure 2.12, Side by side comparison for a Digital Twin

2.4.2 Simulation Software in Medical Device Production

RoboDK has emerged as a widely adopted digital twin platform in the medical device sector, particularly for applications involving catheter assembly automation. It supports offline programming and simulation for a range of industrial robots including those from ABB, Fanuc, KUKA and Universal Robots, allowing engineers to model and validate robotic operations without interrupting live production (Garcia and Wang 2022).

By replicating real world manufacturing conditions, RoboDK simulations help identify workflow inefficiencies, reduce cycle times and ensure collision free operation. The platforms compatibility with PLC logic I/O mapping, and external device integration further supports seamless automation development and process refinement. In this way, RoboDK enhances production planning, reduces commissioning time and increases system reliability while maintaining compliance with good manufacturing standards.

2.4.3 Integration of Robotics & PLCs for Seamless Automation

In an automated assembly line, robotics must operate in synchronisation to ensure accurate sequencing and process reliability. Digital twins enable engineers to simulate and optimise these interactions in advance, reducing setup time and minimising integration errors. This virtual validation ensures smooth communication between robots and PLCs (Benedettini 2020).

2.4.4 Robot-PLC Communication via Industrial Protocols

Digital twin simulations ensure real-time control and data exchange by integrating robotic arms, PLCs, and vision systems through industrial communication protocols. Profinet, commonly used with Siemens systems, enables high-speed robot-to-PLC data exchange, ensuring precise motion control and synchronisation. Ethernet/IP, widely implemented with Allen-Bradley and Fanuc Systems, facilitates seamless connectivity between PLC logic and robotic planning, optimising assembly sequencing and error handling. These protocols enhance interoperability, allowing real time adjustments to robotic motions and improving overall process accuracy (M. Raj *et al.* 2021).

Figure 2.13, Digital twin architecture for virtual simulation and physical reality technology. MS Visio

These protocols enhance interoperability across platforms, allowing real time modifications to robot behaviour and contributing to process consistency, traceability and regulatory compliance.

Figure 2.13 illustrates a system framework where virtual simulation and physical reality are integrated through digital twin architecture, supporting real time communication for human-robot interaction and HMI optimisation.

2.4.5 Vision guided Robotics for Part Positioning

Digital twins enhance vision-guided robotic systems by improving part positioning in catheter manufacturing. AI-powered camera systems detect orientation of the catheter and send precise coordinates to the robotic arms, ensuring accurate insertion and welding. Cognex Vision Systems, for instance, analyse the surface integrity of the catheter, reducing defect rates through automated quality control (Siemens AG 2023a). By simulating camera-robot interactions, manufacturers can train machine vision models in a virtual environment, improving inspection accuracy before implementing the systems in the real world (R. Kumar and J. Lee 2021).

2.4.6 Force/Torque Control for Delicate Assembly Tasks

Catheter assembly requires high-precision force control to prevent damage during bonding, welding, and insertion. Digital twin simulations optimise robotic force application by using force-sensitive end effectors that adjust grip strength based on the catheter's material properties, ensuring damage-free handling. Torque sensors monitor tube insertion pressure to verify proper welding force, enhancing product reliability (Y. Zhang *et al.* 2023). These simulations enable engineers to fine-tune handling strategies, minimising product defect and production downtime.

2.4.7 Human-Machine Interface (HMI) for Operator Control

The Human Machine Interface (HMI) is a central component of modern industrial automation systems, providing operators with live access to production data, control functions, and system diagnostics. In catheter manufacturing, HMIs facilitate interaction with critical equipment such as robotic arms, PLCs, conveyors and vision systems. Operators can use the HMI to monitor cycle time, sensor feedback, welding parameters and alarms states, ensuring that production remains efficient and within specification.

With the adoption of digital twin technology, HMIs are no longer static dashboards but part of a dynamic, interconnected virtual environment. HMIs can be developed and tested within simulation platforms such as RoboDK and Siemens WinCC, allowing engineers to validate user interface logic, button layouts, alarm handling sequences and display accuracy before deployment. This pre-validation reduces implementation time, minimises errors and ensures ergonomic and intuitive interaction for the user.

A key advantage of HMI integration in catheter manufacture is its ability to support flexible, operator driven adjustments to robotic sequences, PLC logic, and inspection tolerances. Operators can initiate recipe changes, update device specific parameters, and reset alarms without the need for manual intervention on the factory floor. This improves responsiveness and production uptime, especially in regulated environments where downtime directly impacts output and compliance.

HMIs often serve as a bridge between local automation layers and supervisory control systems like SCADA. They allow for role-based access control, ensuring that authorised personnel can make changes while maintaining audit trails for traceability. Integration with regulatory frameworks such as FDA 21 CFR Part 11 and ISO 13485 is essential for ensuring compliance in medical device manufacturing.

*Figure 2.14, displays a Siemens HMI interface used in catheter production, highlighting real time data visualisation, robotic stats indicators, and user-controlled parameter inputs.
Siemens.com*

2.5 Environmental and Sustainability Regulations

Medical device manufacturers in Ireland must comply with environmental regulations enforced by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and aligned with the EU Industrial Emissions Directive (IED). The adoption of automated production lines supports these requirements by reducing material waste, optimising energy usage, and enabling predictive maintenance strategies (EPA 2023).

SCADA and IoT enabled monitoring systems facilitate real time energy tracking, helping facilities meet ISO 50001 energy management standards. Robotic automation reduces process variability and raw material waste, contributing to sustainable manufacturing practices in line with Ireland's Circular Economy Action Plan (European Commission 2023).

2.5.1 Environmental Regulation and Protection

As Ireland aligns with EU regulations like the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) and the Climate Action Plan, manufacturers, including those in medical device production, must reduce environmental impacts while maintaining high production standards. In catheter manufacturing, automation can improve efficiency, reduce material waste, energy consumption and emissions.

The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) enforces regulations such as the IED, requiring manufacturers to meet strict standards on emissions, waste, and energy use. For catheter manufacturers, managing emissions and energy consumption in processes like assembly and sterilisation is crucial. By adopting energy-efficient robotics and AI-driven maintenance, catheter production can meet sustainability goals while improving efficiency.

2.5.2 Impact of Automation on EPA Compliance and Sustainability

The integration of robotics and automation in catheter manufacturing can play a crucial role in helping companies meet EPA regulations and sustainability goals. By reducing waste, automated systems enhance precision and reduce defects in catheter assembly, leading to lower material consumption and reduced disposal costs, thereby ensuring compliance with EPA waste management guidelines.

Smart automation solutions such as SCADA and IoT enabled monitoring systems, optimise energy use in production facilities. Real time tracking of energy consumption helps identify inefficiencies, reducing power consumption and aligning with the EPA's National Climate Policy Framework. Automation supports sustainable manufacturing practices by enabling the reuse and recycling of materials, improving process control, and facilitating predictive maintenance to extend equipment lifespan, in line with the EPA's circular economy goals.

2.5.3 Regulatory Reporting and Compliance with the EPA

Regulatory reporting is an essential for ensuring environmental compliance under Irish EPA guidelines and EU directives. Catheter manufacturers must document emissions, waste, water usage and energy consumption as part of their Industrial Emissions (IE) licensing obligations.

Automation technologies such as SCADA, IoT, and real time monitoring simplify data collection and reporting, making it easier to comply with EPA audits and proactively manage environmental performance. These digital systems also improve transparency and allow early intervention when deviations occur.

Any environmental incident such as emissions breaches or equipment capacity exceedance, must be reported immediately to the EPA. As automation and data analytics evolve, regulatory reporting is becoming more effect, helping manufacturers align with Irelands climate targets while maintaining high production standards.

2.6 Challenges and Considerations in Automation

2.6.1 Environmental and Regulatory Barries

While automation provides significant sustainability benefits, several challenges must be addressed to ensure alignment with environmental regulations. One key issue is energy source dependency. Robotics and automation systems require electricity to operate, and their net environmental benefit is closely linked to whether the facility is powered by renewable energy or fossil fuels. The EPA encourages industries to transition to low carbon energy sources to maximise emissions reduction and comply with national climate goals

Another important consideration is electronic waste (e-waste). The installation, maintenance and eventual disposal of robotic and control systems contribute to e-waste generation. Compliance with the Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive is essential to ensure responsible recycling and disposal of outdated automation hardware.

Finally, automated manufacturing lines must incorporate environmental monitoring systems to track emissions, waste output and energy consumption in real time. This data is vital for meeting EPA audit requirements and maintaining ongoing compliance with the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED). SCADA and IoT based systems enable real time logging, which supports both operational transparency and proactive environmental management.

2.6.2 Technical Challenges and Future Trends in Catheter Manufacturing

Although automation has advanced significantly in medical device manufacturing, catheter production continues to present technical challenges. The assembly of catheters involves handling small, flexible, and delicate materials that require high precision, making them difficult or for traditional robotic systems to manipulate without causing damage or misalignments (International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) 2021). Vision systems may also struggle to detect micro defects or bonding inconsistencies in transparent tubing, reducing the reliability of automated quality control.

Another major challenge is the integration of automation within stringent regulatory frameworks such as ISO 13485, GMP, and GAMP 5, all of which require extensive validation, documentation, and traceability (ISPE 2021). These regulatory demands often increase the time and cost of adopting new technologies.

To address these limitations, manufacturers are exploring AI-driven inspection, adaptive robotics, and predictive maintenance. Machine learning algorithms can enhance defect detection and pattern recognition beyond the capabilities of traditional rule-based systems (ISO/ASTM International n.d.). Meanwhile, force sensitive robotic arms improve insertion and cutting accuracy, and predictive maintenance powered by IoT sensors helps minimise unplanned downtime (ASTM F2792 2013).

2.6.3 Lean and Six Sigma Principals in Catheter Manufacturing

Lean and Six Sigma methodologies are widely adopted in the medical device industry to minimise waste, improve quality and optimise process efficiency. In the context of catheter manufacturing, these principals help reduce nonvalue added activities, control variation in assembly processes and enhance consistency in product quality.

Lean focuses on eliminating inefficiencies such as excess handling, waiting time and overproduction which are issues that are often prevalent in manual catheter assembly. Through automation and digital simulation, this project applied Lean thinking by streamlining material flow, reducing handling steps and integrating simulated monitoring to minimise downtime.

Six Sigma's DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve, Control) framework aligns with structured engineering workflow used in this thesis. Key performance indicators such as defect rate, cycle time and equipment efficiency were measured and analysed using Power BI, enabling data driven process refinement. Vision system integration ensured defect detection within tolerance limits, contributing to tighter process control.

By integrating Lean and Six Sigma principles into the system design and analysis stages, the project supports the development of a scalable, quality focused manufacturing line that aligns with industry best practices and regulatory expectations (Performance Consultants 2023)

2.7 Regulatory Compliance in Medical Device Manufacturing

Building on the challenges identified in Section 2.6, this section reviews the regulatory frameworks and industry best practices that provide guidance for the effective and compliant implementation of automation in catheter manufacturing.

2.7.1 ISO 13485 and GMP Compliance in Automated Manufacturing

To address the regulatory and quality challenges associated with automation, medical device manufacturers must comply with international standards such as ISO 13485:2016 and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP). ISO 13485 outlines the requirements for a quality Management System (QMS), emphasizing risk-based process validation, traceability and document control in both manual and automated production environments (International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 2016). In the context of catheter manufacturing, automated systems such as PLC-controlled robots ensure repeatable process execution, helping maintain compliance and reduce variability.

GMP regulations mandate that every step of production such as raw material handling, equipment calibration, environmental control and staff training is documented and validated to ensure consistent product quality (WHO 2020). Unlike traditional quality assurance that relies heavily on final product testing, GMP requires risk to be mitigated throughout the entire manufacturing process, particularly in automation where hidden faults may not be visually detectable.

Figure 2.15, The 5 P's of GMP. MS Excel

Figure 2.15: The 5 Ps of Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) – illustrating the key elements manufacturers must manage to maintain product quality and regulatory compliance in automated medical device production.

In engineering terms, GxP (Good Practice) serves as an umbrella for GMP and related standards. GxP systems are categorised as:

- GxP (Quality-Critical Systems): Including sterilisation units, cleanroom controls, vision inspection systems and force/torque sensors.
- GEP (Good Engineering Practice): Non quality critical systems like data historians or building management tools used for support and monitoring (ISPE, 2016).

Sterilisation processes are a key component of GMP in catheter manufacturing. Systems such as Ethylene Oxide (EtO) sterilisation, autoclaving, and UV/HPV disinfection must be fully validated and controlled. Automation enhances these processes by regulating cycle parameters (temperature, humidity, and exposure time) through PLCs and monitoring then via SCADA for traceability and compliance with standards such as ISO 11135 and ISO 14937.

Together, ISO 13485, GMP, and their supporting systems ensure that automated catheter production meets the strict requirements for safety, consistency, and regulatory acceptance.

2.7.2 GAMP 5 and Automation Validation

Automated catheter production systems must comply with GAMP 5 guidelines, which offer a structured, risk-based approach to validating computerised systems in regulated environments. Key components such as PLC logic, robotic control software and vision system algorithms require documented validation to ensure repeatability, accuracy and data integrity (ISPE 2021). The use of digital twins enables simulation and testing of production processes in a virtual environment, helping identify risks early and streamline validation. This supports compliance with ISO 13485 and reduces delays in deployment.

2.7.3 Packaging, Labelling, and Compliance Control Systems

Automated packaging and sterile sealing systems maintain sterility of catheter products, particularly for blister packs and pouches (ISO 11607:2019 2019). Unique Device Identification (UDI) and label verification systems ensure proper tracking for products and regulatory compliance under FDA 21 CFR Part 801, 2022.

To support compliance and data integrity, Electronic Batch Records (EBR) provide full product traceability in line with FDA 21 CFR Part 11, while Process Analytical Technology (PAT) enables real time quality monitoring to reduce defect rates and ensuring that production outputs remain consistent with regulatory and industry standards (ISPE 2021).

2.7.4 FDA 21 CFR Part 11: Electronic Records and Data Integrity

As catheter manufacturing adopts automation, vast amounts of electronic data are generated by vision systems, PLCs and SCADA platforms. FDA 21 CFR Part 11 mandates the integrity, traceability and security of these records through audit trails, user authentication and data encryption (FDA (2022) 2022). Integrated SCADA systems enable real time process monitoring and secure electronic batch record storage, ensuring full compliance with regulatory requirements and supporting robust quality management (ISPE 2021).

2.8 Outlook

The reviews literature suggests a strong trajectory towards increasingly intelligent and integrated automation in catheter manufacturing. As technologies such as AI, digital twins, and industrial IoT continue to evolve, future production systems are expected to become more autonomous, data driven and responsive. The shift from manual or semi-automated processes to fully connected smart factories is anticipated to improve not only productivity but also regulatory compliance and sustainability.

In particular, the use of digital twins is projected to expand, enabling real time simulation, predictive maintenance and dynamic optimisation of robotic and PLC-controlled processes. Vision systems powered by deep learning will likely achieve higher accuracy in defect detection, even in transparent or flexible catheter components, while adaptive robotics will enhance handling of delicate materials with minimal human intervention.

Regulatory frameworks such as ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 11 are expected to place increasing emphasis on traceability, cyber security and electronic record integrity, driving the adoption of compliant SCADA and data analytics platforms. Overall, automation will remain central to meeting the growing demand for high precision, cost effective and sustainable catheter production.

3. Methodology and System Design

3.1 Introduction to Methodology

The methodology in this study followed a structured approach to developing an automated catheter manufacturing system. It integrated industrial automation, robotics, and advanced quality control techniques to improve production efficiency, minimise human error, and ensure compliance with medical device regulations. This methodology consists of several key stages, including system design, automation integration, process validation and regulatory testing.

To achieve a high precision manufacturing workflow, the system incorporates robotic automation for material handling, PLC and SCADA based control systems for coordinated process management, and vision inspection systems for real time defect detection. The digital twin simulations were used to optimise process parameters prior to physical implementation. The integration of AI quality control a predictive maintenance algorithm further enhances system reliability and operational efficiency.

3.2 Robotic System and Motion Planning

The robotic system in this study was designed to automate catheter handling, cutting and packaging, reducing manual intervention while ensuring precision in manufacturing. The setup consists of a dual-robot configuration, where each robot was assigned specific tasks to optimise workflow efficiency.

Please Refer to Appendix B – RoboDK Simulations, for Robotic System Flow Chart.

Robot 1 was responsible for picking and placing catheter tubes onto the cutting station, while Robot 2 performed precise cutting operations and transferred the processed tubes on to the second conveyor system. The conveyor facilitated the movement of the cut tube to a conveyor system. The second conveyor facilitated the movement of cut tubes to the packaging station, where Robot 2 handled the final placement of tubes into packaging boxes, which ensured an organised stacking pattern. This workflow was modular and can be adapted for a single-robot configuration if efficiency studies indicate a more streamlined approach.

The robotic motion planning strategy was developed in RoboDK, where offline programming and digital twin simulations allowed for precise control over robot movements. Motion planning ensured collision-free path execution by preventing interference between robots and minimising cycle times by eliminating unnecessary movements. The system incorporated adaptive gripping and placement strategies to accommodate variations in catheter tube size and material properties. Kinematic simulations, force feedback integration, and AI trajectory adjustments contributed to smooth handling while preventing tube deformation or damage.

3.3 End-of-Arm Tooling (EOAT) Design

The design of the End-of-Arm Tooling (EOAT) was a critical aspect of the robotics systems, ensuring precise and reliable handling of catheter tubes during manufacturing. In this project, the Robotiq Hand-E adaptive gripper was selected and simulated within RoboDK, offering a compact and versatile mechanical gripping solution specifically suited to delicate handling tasks, such as catheter tube transfer and positioning.

The EOAT was responsible for gripping, aligning, and transporting catheter tubes between different process stations including loading, cutting, and inspection while preserving the materials integrity. The Robotiq Hand-E gripper, with its force sensitive adaptive fingers provided the capability to dynamically adjust grip strength, making it suitable for handling flexible, semi-rigid tubing without causing deformation or slippage. This aligns with established practices for robotic gripping in the medical device industry, where both reliability and repeatability are essential (R. Bogue 2021).

Figure 3.1, Robotiq Hand-E Gripper and RoboDK Digital Twin

Initial gripper selection considered both vacuum and mechanical designs. Vacuum grippers offer non-contact handling, reducing contamination risk, but may struggle with long, flexible tubing due to surface inconsistencies and low structural rigidity. The mechanical approach by the Robotiq gripper, proved more suitable by offering controller contact and reliable retention during robot motion, particularly in tasks like cutting and force monitored insertion (John Wiley & Sons and G. J. Monkman 2017).

To accommodate various catheter diameters, the Hand-E grippers adjustable grip range and integrated force feedback were leveraged to handle multiple product sizes without requiring tool changes. This adaptability significantly reduces downtime and

enhances operational flexibility in production lines handling different product variants (M. Tavakoli *et al.* 2018). Force and torque sensing capabilities also play a crucial role during precision-critical steps such as tube insertion and pre-weld positioning, where consistent pressure is vital to avoid material damage (M. Pfeifer *et al.* 2020).

By incorporating an adaptive, force sensitive EOAT, the robotic system simulated in RoboDK ensures high precision catheter handling, minimising material defects and supporting a reliable and scalable automation workflow.

3.4 PLC Integration and Control Logic

The Siemens S7-1500 PLC (CPU 1516-3 PN/DP) was selected for the automated catheter manufacturing system due to its high processing power, advanced diagnostics, and seamless integration with industrial robotics and vision systems. This PLC acted as the central controller for coordinating robot sequences, conveyor movement, vision inspection triggers and safety interlocks.

Communication between the UR5e robotic arm and the PLC was achieved via Profinet, enabling real time, deterministic data exchange. This ensured precise synchronisation between robotic tasks and conveyor operations, which was essential for maintaining product flow and reducing cycle times.

Control logic was developed in Siemens TIA Portal, where ladder diagrams were used to manage process sequences such as robot initiation, conveyor activation and emergency stop routines. Safety interlocks were implemented to ensure the system could immediately halt operations in the event of an error or obstruction, in line with industrial safety standards.

To control conveyor movement, a SIMOREG DC Master drive equipped with the CBE20 communication module was simulated as part of the system. This drive enabled fine control of a DC motor and communicated with the PLC over Profibus, ensuing smooth, coordinated motion of the conveyor in line with robot tasks. The inclusion of the SIMOREG reflects realistic industrial scenarios, especially in facilities using legacy or hybrid motor systems.

Before deployment, the control logic was validated through TIA Portals simulation tools, allowing all input/output mappings and safety logic to be tested under virtual conditions. This verification stage ensured that the system performed reliably, and that the PLC could respond effectively to all runtime conditions, including force feedback, vision triggers and emergency stops.

Please refer to Appendix E – Siemens PLC Program Overview for PLC code details.

3.5 Vision System Integration for Quality Control

The vision system for quality inspection in this automated catheter manufacturing system utilised Cognex 3800 series cameras, which are known for their high-resolution images and fast processing capabilities, crucial for real-time defect detection (Cognex 2021). These cameras were selected for their ability to capture detailed images of the catheter tubes at various stages of the manufacturing process, which enabled precise verification of tube dimensions, alignment and surface integrity.

Machine vision tasks include verifying tube dimensions and alignment to ensure they meet the required specifications. The system is also tasked with detecting surface defects such as cracks, contamination, and misalignment that may affect the overall quality and functionality of the final product. By using advanced image processing techniques, the Cognex system can quickly identify even the smallest defects, significantly improving the accuracy of quality control (M. Raj *et al.* 2021).

Figure 3.2, Vision Suite Interface with Results

Figure 3.2 displays the Cognex Vision Suite interface during a real time inspection of a catheter tube. Edge detection tools were applied to accurately identify the tubes outer badineries, ensuring correct alignment and dimensional conformity. The visual inspection step helps detect structural irregularities, such as bends or misplacements, prior to packaging. Please refer to Appendix C – Cognex Vision System for all visual inspection related material.

The Cognex Vision Suite interface was used to configure inspection parameters and view simulated results. AI based tools, including Cognex SnAPP software, enabled adaptive learning and enhanced defect detection accuracy by recognising pattern deviations and adapting to variable conditions. This data driven approach improved system reliability over time, reducing both false positives and negatives. (R. Kumar and J. Lee 2021).

The vision system is integrated with the Siemens PLC and SCADA platform, enabling automated quality control. The PLC received real-time image data from the Cognex cameras, and based on this information, it can adjust the production line in real time. Stopping the process in the event of a defect or in the case of realigning a tube, alerts were sent for manual intervention. The SCADA system allows operators to monitor quality metrics and intervene when necessary.

3.6 SCADA System for Process Monitoring

The SCADA system, specifically Siemens WinCC, was central to the real time monitoring and control of the catheter manufacturing process. WinCC provides a robust platform for data acquisition, enabling the continuous tracking of critical process variables, including force, temperature, and cycle time. These real-time metrics are essential for ensuring that the production process adheres to the specified parameters and that any deviations were detected promptly (Siemens AG 2023b).

One of the key functionalities of the Siemens WinCC SCADA system was the alarm and error handling. The system was programmed to send automated alerts when any process variations deviate from their acceptable ranges, such as a force exceeding predefined limits or temperature fluctuations during the welding process. These alerts help operators respond immediately to issues, reducing the risk of defective products or production downtime. The system can also be configured to trigger defective shutdown or corrective actions if critical thresholds are breached, enforcing safety and quality standards are consistently met.

Power BI was used to visualise and analyse production data from the system, acting as a supplementary SCADA dashboard. Simulated datasets were imported to represent key metrics such as cycle time trends, defect rates, equipment performance and operator interaction statistics. These dashboards provided a higher level of overview of production health, helping identify bottlenecks and areas for optimisation. Power BI also enabled traceability and trend analysis, aligning with the goals of predictive maintenance and regulatory documentation.

Win CC and Power BI together offer complementary monitoring tools with WinCC focusing on real time control and fault management, and Power BI enhancing post process analytics and decision making. This dual approach improved operational transparency, supporting immediate response and long term process optimisation.

Figure 3.3, Siemens WinCC Simatic HMI layout

Figure 3.3 displays the Siemens WinCC Simatic HMI layout developed for the manufacturing system. The interface provides real time visibility into key process variables such as start/stop, fault reset and fault control.

3.7 CAD Modelling and Material Selection

As part of system design, key components of the catheter manufacturing line were modelled in SolidWorks to ensure accurate for, function and integration with robotic workflows. The most critical mechanical assembly developed was the cutting station, which required high stability and material compatibility for medical grade components.

Stainless steel 304 was selected for the body of the cutting station due to its excellent corrosion resistance, mechanical strength, and compliance with ISO 10993 and ASTM F138 standards for biocompatibility in medical device manufacturing. This material also offers ease of sterilisation and resistance to wear, making it suitable for long term use in cleanroom environments. Non-load bearing structural components and sensor mounts were designed using ABD plastic to reduce weight and cost.

These CAD models were exported in STL format and imported into RoboDK for digital twin simulation. This enabled alignment validation, collision checking, a workflow refinement prior to physical deployment.

3.8 Packaging Automation

The packaging automation process in catheter manufacturing focused on optimising the placement and arrangement of finished products into packaging boxes, ensuring that each package met the required specifications for both safety and space efficiency. A key part of packaging automation was the development of box-filling strategies, where the arrangement of catheter tubes within the box was carefully planned based on their dimensions and required packaging standards. This process involves arranging the tubes in a compact yet secure manner to prevent damage during transportation and storage.

To achieve precise placement of the tubes within the packaging boxes, robot-assisted tracking systems were employed. These systems use vision-guided robotics to determine the exact positioning of each tube before it was placed into the box. Using real-time data from the Cognex Vision system, the robots could adjust their movements to place the tubes accurately without causing misalignment or damage. The robots also ensure that the placement follows the predefined packaging pattern, further enhancing efficiency and reducing the chances of human error in the process.

Figure 3.4, RoboDK – Packaging Sequence

The packaging process was integrated with two conveyors and the PLC system for cycle synchronisation. The conveyor system was responsible for transporting the tubes from the assembly line to the packaging station. The PLC coordinates the operation of robots and conveyors to ensure the conveyor belt, and the system maintains a consistent flow of tubes into the packaging area, minimising downtime and optimising throughput. The Siemens PLC managed coordination between robot movement, conveyor timing and packaging cycles, adjusting speed and sequencing based on the programme code. This allowed continuous flow and minimised downtime.

Overall, packaging automation enhanced the efficiency, speed and accuracy of the packaging process, ensuring that catheter tubes are packed securely and efficiently, while reducing the reliance on manual labour and minimising the risk of errors. By integrating advanced robotics, vision systems, and PLC based control, the system can achieve higher levels of automation precision in the packaging stage of production.

3.9 Digital Twin for System Optimisation

The implementation of the digital twin enabled the simulation and optimisation of the catheter manufacturing process before physical deployment. A digital twin is the replica of the production system that integrates both live and simulated data to the process models to enhance efficiency and detect potential issues (F. Tao *et al.* 2019).

RoboDK was used for virtual simulation of the robotic workflow, allowing engineers to program, validate and optimise robot trajectories before deploying them on the actual production floor. The digital twin provided an accurate kinematic model of the robotic system, enabling collision detection, cycle time estimation, and task feasibility analysis (R. Bogue 2022). By simulating the robotic motion, engineers can refine movement paths to minimise energy consumption, reduce unnecessary movements, and improve overall system efficiency (D. Kaplan *et al.* 2020).

A key advantage of the digital twin was the ability to validate process efficiency before real world implementation. By simulating various operating scenarios, it ensured that robot movements, material handling, and processing times are optimised. This approach significantly reduced the need for physical trials. Lowering setup costs and production downtime. It also allowed for early detection of errors, which can allow a seamless transition from simulation to reality (T. H.-J. Uhlemann *et al.* 2017).

The digital twin assisted in identifying bottlenecks in production. By continuously monitoring workflow efficiency, the simulation highlighted slow process stages, excessive wait times, or inefficiencies in robot coordination. Engineers can then adjust parameters such as conveyor speeds, robot timing, and task sequencing to eliminate bottlenecks and improve throughput. The integration of real-time feedback into the digital twin enables adaptive control and predictive maintenance, ensuring long-term system performance (R. Rosen *et al.* 2015).

Figure 3.5, A side-by-side comparison between the RoboDK simulation and the real UR5e robot setup further illustrates the accuracy and alignment achieved using the digital twin.

Figure 3.5 leverages digital twin technology, catheter production can be optimised with greater precision, reduced costs, and enhanced process reliability, ultimately improving manufacturing scalability and compliance with medical device production standards.

3.10 Experimental Setup and Validation

The experimental validation and testing phase ensured the automated catheter manufacturing system met operational and regulatory standards. It included several stages: unit testing, integration testing, performance evaluation, and regulatory compliance checks.

During performance evaluation, key metrics such as cycle time, defect detection rate, and overall system throughput were assessed to determine how well the system met its efficiency and repeatability objectives.

Regulatory compliance checks confirmed alignment with medical device manufacturing standards, including ISO 13485, GMP, and GAMP 5. As part of a FAT validation, the system was designed to undergo IQ (Installation Qualification), OQ (Operational Qualification), and PQ (Performance Qualification), ensuring the equipment was installed correctly, operated within defined parameters, and consistently performed as intended.

Comprehensive traceability and documentation practices were also established, ensuring that all testing procedures, results and system changes were recorded to support regulatory audits and future system upgrades.

Table 3.1, Functional Unit Testing Matrix for Automated Catheter Assembly Line

Test ID	Test Description	Preconditions	Pass/Fail
FT-01	Verify the robot picks and places correctly	System powered on, PLC program running, robot homed	✓
FT-02	Check robot speed and waypoint accuracy	Robot calibrated; predefined waypoints set	✓
FT-03	Ensure PLC executes process logic correctly	All sensors and actuators connected; program uploaded	✓
FT-04	Verify E-Stop halts all system operations	E-Stop enabled, robot running	✓
FT-05	Confirm conveyor starts, stops, and adjusts speed correctly via VFD	VFD connected, PLC sending control signals	✓
FT-06	Ensure vision system correctly identifies pass/fail products	Camera aligned, lighting adjusted, trained vision model	✓
FT-07	Test failed product rejection mechanism	Vision system detects a failed product	✓
FT-08	Validate pneumatic actuators extend and retracts on command	Air supply on, solenoid valves functional	✓
FT-09	Ensure all subsystems communicate correctly (Robot to PLC to Vision)	Communication protocols configured	✓
FT-10	Test operator indication system (stack lights, alarm)	PLC sends signals for pass/fail/product absence	✓

Unit testing was conducted to validate the functionality of industrial subsystems within the automated catheter manufacturing line. Each test focused on a specific component of the robot motion, PLC logic execution, conveyor control or vision system performance. Table 3.1 outlines ten key functional tests (FT-01 to FT-10), confirming completion of critical processes including emergency stops, inter device communication and actuator control. These tests helped verify system readiness prior to full integration and performance testing.

3.11 Summary of Methodology and Future Improvements

This study presented a structured methodology by developing an automated catheter manufacturing system. By integrating robotic automation for material handling, Siemens S7-1500 PLCs for process control, Cognex 3800 vision systems for real time defect detection, and SCADA systems for continuous process monitoring, the system was designed to improve efficiency, accuracy and regulatory compliance. Digital twin simulations in RoboDK enabled pre-deployment validation and optimisation of robotic motion, while AI-enhanced quality control and predictive maintenance further increased system reliability.

Future improvements could focus on AI-driven optimisation of robotic trajectories and defect classification, reducing false positives and improving quality assurance. Enhanced IoT integration would support predictive maintenance, live data monitoring and smarter resource allocation. Adaptive gripping mechanisms could allow safer handling of various catheter sizes and materials, and collaborative robots (cobots) may offer greater flexibility in hybrid workflows. Integrating cloud-based SCADA platforms would support remote access and live decision making, ensuring continuous improvement and scalability in line with evolving industry standards.

4. Implementation

4.1 Digital Twin Development and Workflow Simulation

4.1.1 Creation of Digital Twin in RoboDK

A digital twin of the catheter manufacturing process was developed using RoboDK to virtually represent the entire automated system. This simulation environment enabled comprehensive process planning, including collision section, motion path optimisation and task sequencing, all before physical implementation. The RoboDK digital twin served as a foundation for iterative testing and refinement, ensuring that the designed workflow was feasible, effect and aligned eight the physical constraints of the actual setup.

4.1.2 Process Workflow Modelling and Validation

The process began with the creation of CAD models in SolidWorks, representing the key components of the catheter assembly line such as the cutting station. This model was exported as a STEP file and imported into RoboDK for digital twin development. RoboDK's integrated kinematic solvers and motion planning tools were used to define robot paths for tasks such as catheter tube handling, cutting, inspection and packaging. The simulation environment allowed for iterative refinement of each motion sequence, ensuring efficient workflow, collision free operation and minimal cycle time.

Figure 4.1, RoboDK Workflow layout

4.1.3 Simulation of Force Sensor Feedback and Quality Control

The digital twin was used to simulate force and torque responses based on the UR5e robots built in sensors, reflecting real world handling behaviour within the RoboDK environment. While no external force sensors were used, the simulated responses allowed the system to assess handling dynamics and detect when excessive pressure could lead to catheter deformation. Vision inspection tasks were also simulated, ensuring that the robots positioning aligned with the conveyor movement and camera field of view. This integration helped verify that quality control functions such as defect detection and alignment checks would operate reliably under realistic production conditions.

Figure 4.2, Cognex Vison Suite: Edge Detection of Catheter Tube

Figure 4.2 shows the implementation of edge detection within Cognex Vison Suite during the digital twin simulation. The software identifies the contour and alignment of the catheter tube using fine segment tools allowing the system to verify the correct positioning and defects of the device.

4.1.4 Benefits of the Digital Twin approach

The implementation of a digital twin significantly reduced the reliance on physical prototyping by enabling virtual testing and validation of the entire production workflow. Robotic sequence, collision detection, and cycle timing could be evaluated in advance, allowing for early identification and resolution of integration issues. This pre-deployment validation minimised setup time and reduced the likelihood for rework and improved system reliability.

4.2 Robotic Path Planning and Execution

4.2.1 Path Optimisation in RoboDK

Path planning was a critical component in ensuring accurate and efficiency movement during catheter manufacturing. RoboDK was used to define and simulate the trajectories for the UR5e robotic arms performing tasks such as tube placement, cutting and packaging.

Using RoboDK's trajectory generation tools, each robot's motion was optimised by considering workspace constraints, joint limits and the reachability required for precise handling. These planned paths ensured smooth movement and task specific efficiency while avoiding unnecessary repositing that could increase cycle time.

Figure 4.3, RoboDK – Path trajectory and optimisation

One of the key features applied was RoboDK's collision detection. By replicating the physical environment including robots, conveyors and fixtures, the software identified and prevented potential interference between components.

The toolpaths were visualised and validated within RoboDK before deployment, ensuing reliable execution on the physical system. This process significantly reduced trial and error during implementation, supporting high output, repeatability and system safety.

4.2.2 Programming and Execution on UR5e

The UR5e robot was programmed using RoboDK's offline programming environment, allowing for the generation of executable URScript code tailed to the catheter manufacturing workflow. RoboDK's drag and drop interface and integrated post processes enabled seamless conversion of simulated paths into robot specific code, reducing programming time and ensuring compatibility with the physical UR5e controller. The program was generated as a URP file for the UR5e Teach Pendant.

The robots task sequence included picking raw catheter tubes from the input station, placing them onto the cutting platform, and finally transferring the processed tubes to the packaging conveyor. Through RoboDK's real time simulation tools, adjustments were made to minimise wrist rotation, optimise TCP orientation, and reduce unnecessary travel.

Execution was validated through RoboDK's robot driver, which allowed the simulation to be mirrored on the UR5e in real time. The onboard Teach Pendant (Figure 4.4) was used to calibrate tool positions, refine waypoints, and test safety stops. UR's built in force and torque sensors ensured gentle handling during tube placement, especially when interacting with the cutting assembly.

Figure 4.4, UR5e Teach Pendant for the Digital Twin

4.2.3 Assembly Verification Using Built in Sensors

The UR5e robots integrated force and torque sensors were essential for ensuring safe and precise handling of catheter tubes during the assembly process. These sensors enabled feedback monitoring during critical tasks such as tube insertion and positioning, allowing the system to adapt dynamically and minimise the risk of damage. By adjusting its movements in response to resistance levels, the robot maintained consistent force application, reducing the likelihood of deformation or misalignment during bonding.

To validate the robots handling safety and estimate the forces encountered during the cutting stage, a torque simulation was performed in MATLAB. This simulation modelled the torque range based on the estimated payload, robot configuration, and a 30 cm lever arm for the base. The results showed torque values between 4.43-6.68 Nm, confirming that the system remained within a safe operational envelope, even under ± 2 mm positional offsets.

Figure 4.5, Simulated Torque Response During Tube Handling (MATLAB).

Figure 4.5 shows the torque estimation results for UR5e robot during catheter cutting, validating safe handling through MATLAB modelling. Please refer to Appendix H – MATLAB Torque Simulation for the simulation code.

4.3 PLC and Control Logic Integration

4.3.1 Siemens S7-1500 I/O Mapping and Ladder Logic

The Siemens S7-1500 PLC (CPU 1516-3 PN/DP) served as the central controller for the catheter manufacturing system, coordinating communication between all hardware components. I/O mapping was completed within the TIA Portal, where digital and analogue signals were assigned to devices such as the UR5e robot, conveyor drives (via the SIMATIC DCM), Cognex vision system, and HMI. The Cognex In-Sight camera was imported using GSDML files, allowing for native integration and diagnostics.

Figure 4.6, TIA Portal Network View of Siemens S7-1500 Automation System Overview of device interconnection including UR5e robot, Cognex camera, SIMATIC DCM and HMI panel.

Ladder logic was created in TIA Portal to manage key tasks such as robot commands, conveyor control and interlocks to ensure safe, sequential operation. Emergency stop routines and safety checks were included to halt the system if faults were detected. These logic routines were modular and could be reused or extended as system complexity increased.

Using diagnostic tags and offline simulation helped validate control logic early, reducing errors during deployment. Communication between all components was handled via Profinet, enabling high speed synchronisation and system stability. Communication between all components was handled via Profinet, enabling high speed synchronisation and system stability. The consistent communication ensured precise timing between all system components.

Refer to Appendix E – Siemens PLC Overview for the PLC logic and ladder code.

4.3.2 Profinet Communication and Safety Interlocks

Profinet was implemented as the primary industrial communication protocol for real time data exchange between the Siemens S7-1500 PLC, UR5e robotic arms, vision systems and SCADA interface. Its high-speed deterministic performance enabled precise synchronisation of robot motion with conveyor operation and inspection triggers, which was essential for achieving seamless process flow and minimising cycle times.

The Profinet network configuration was carried out in Siemens TIA Portal, where each device was assigned a unique address and integrated into the central control system. Communication between the PLC and the robot was managed via cyclic data exchange, allowing for immediate responses to start signals, inspection results and process completion feedback.

To ensure operator and equipment safety, safety interlocks were programmed into the PLC ladder logic. These included emergency stop (E-stop) handling, system wide fault responses and status monitoring of critical components. If an unsafe condition such as misalignment, sensor fault or proximity breach was detected, the system would automatically halt operations and trigger a visual and audible alarm via SCADA.

Safety rated inputs and outputs were mapped for key functions such as the E-stop push buttons and manual override switches. These safeguards ensured compliance with relevant safety standards and supported the validation processes required under ISO 13849 and IEC 62061 for functional safety in automated systems.

4.3.3 Conveyor and Robot Synchronisation

Synchronisation between the conveyor system and robotic arms was essential to maintain the flow of catheter components across each production stage. The Siemens S7-1500 PLC coordinated the conveyor belt motion with robot activities through precise I/O mapping and Profinet-based communication.

The PLC monitored the conveyors sensor inputs to determine when a catheter tube was correctly positioned at each processing station. Based on this signal, the PLC sent commands to the UR5e robot to initiate picking, cutting, or packaging actions. After each operation, the PLC triggered the conveyor to advance to the next station, maintaining a continuous and timed workflow.

Feedback loops ensured that robots only performed tasks when the product was properly aligned and ready. In the event of a delay or misalignment, the system paused conveyor motion and activated error handling routines through SCADA alerts. This avoided collisions and ensured product integrity during transitions.

This level of synchronisation enabled precise timing between robot actions and conveyor movement, improving output while minimising idle and operational errors. The result was a seamless integration of manual handling, process automation, and quality control across the entire assembly line.

4.4 Vision Systems Implementation: Camera-Based Quality Control

4.4.1 Cognex 3800 Setup and Configuration

The Cognex In-Sight 3800 vision system was selected for its advanced inspection capabilities and built in image processing functionality, making it well suited for incline quality assurance in catheter manufacturing. During system setup, the camera was mounted above the inspection zone with calibrated field of view optimised for capturing images of the catheter tubes as they advanced along the conveyor.

A key feature implemented was edge detection using fine segmentation algorithms, which enabled precise localisation of tube edges for dimensional measurement and alignment validation. This was particularly effective for identifying subtle shifts in tube position and detecting defects at the cutting interfaces. The fine segmentation tools allowed the system to accurately trace edges even on semi-transparent or reflective surfaces common in catheter materials.

Figure 4.7, Comparison of the Cognex Vision Suite edge detection output (top) and the physical catheter tube (bottom), highlighting alignment and defect identification features.

The cameras onboard processing allowed for quick decision making without requiring external computation. Regions of interest (ROI) were defined to focus on critical inspection zones, improving detection speed.

Inspection results were sent to the Siemens PLC via Ethernet, enabling decision making, including triggering alarms or stopping the line when defects were detected. This integration ensured the vision system supported high output while also being an accurate automated quality control system.

4.4.2 Inline AI-Based Defect Detection with Cognex SnAPP

Cognex SnAPP was implemented to enhance the accuracy of defect detection through AI-based image analysis. This tool enabled the system to learn from sample images and identify subtle defects such as microcracks, contamination, or bonding misalignments in tubes.

Unlike traditional rule-based inspection, SnAPP used adaptive deep learning models that improved over-time becoming more accurate at distinguishing between acceptable variations and true defects. This approach significantly reduced false positives and negatives, improving production yield and inspection reliability.

SnAPP operated by analysing each image which was captured by the Cognex 3800 sensor and making rapid pass/fail decisions. The system could flag defects and communicate instantly with the PLC, triggering alerts for pausing the line if necessary. This inline AI capability ensured that defective components were identified early in the process, contributing to higher product quality and regulatory compliance.

4.4.3 Vision System Integration with PLC and Robot

The vision system was tightly integrated with the Siemens S7-1500 PLC and the UR5e robot to enable automated quality control. Upon capturing and analysing images, the Cognex 3800 system transmitted inspection results directly to the PLC via Ethernet. This allowed the system to make live decisions, such as stopping the conveyor or rejecting defective tubes.

The UR5e robot's movements were synchronised with the camera's inspection window, ensuring accurate positioning during image capture. This coordination helped verify proper tube alignment and enabled immediate action on detected defects. Integration with SCADA can provide operators with live feedback, supporting traceability and efficient troubleshooting.

4.5 SCADA and HMI Monitoring System

4.5.1 Siemens WinCC Configuration

Siemens WinCC was used in its basic form through the HMI development environment within TIA Portal. The HMI was designed to interface with the Siemens S7-1500 PLC, allowing operators to monitor and control key elements of the catheter manufacturing process in real time.

Operator ID	No	Yes	Total
OP-001	200	800	1000
Adjusted Conveyor Speed	200		200
Stopped Line for QC		800	800
OP-002		500	500
Reset Robot Alarm		500	500
OP-003	300		300
Changed Inspection Mode	300		300
Total	500	1300	1800

**Cognex
Vision**
First Affected Component

Figure 4.8, Power BI - HMI Interaction with Power BI Dashboard: Cognex Vision System and Operator Action Tracking

Figure 4.8 shows a segment of the Power BI dashboard which visualises the interaction between the operator and the automated catheter production system, showing the data from the HMI interface. The Cognex vision system monitors the quality of components during the production process. When the system detects a defect, it triggers the “stopped for QC” signal, indicating a quality control interruption for further inspection or correction. This table captures the operator’s actions, recording which buttons were pressed and the corresponding stop responses.

The interface provided essential system feedback, such as conveyor status, robot cycle triggers, and basic process alerts. Although advanced SCADA features like data logging and remote access were not implemented in WinCC, core visualisation and control functions were delivered through the integrated HMI panel, ensuring safe and intuitive operator interaction.

4.5.2 Alarm Handling and System Metrics

Alarm handling was implemented directly through the Siemens HMI configured in TIA Portal, the system was designed to trigger visual alerts in response to critical faults such as robot errors conveyor stoppages or failed vision inspections. These alarms provided live feedback to operators, improving responsiveness and ensuring production continuity.

Sum of Response Time (ms) by Action Taken and Operator ID

Figure 4.9, Power BI - Sum of Response Time (ms) by Action Taken and Operator ID

Basic system metrics such as cycle progress, conveyor status and sensor states were also displayed on the HMI. This allows operators to monitor live system behaviour and make manual interventions if needed. While the HMI handled immediate, process data, broader performance analysis and trends were visualised using Power BI dashboards.

4.5.3 Remote Access and Data Logging

Although a full SCADA system was not implemented, Power BI was used as the primary platform for data logging and remote system visualisation. Simulated production data, including cycle times, defect counts, equipment utilisation, and status metrics, were imported into Power BI to mimic live monitoring.

This setup allowed for the variation of dashboards accessible remotely via the Power BI cloud service, providing operators and engineers with visual insights into system performance without needing local access. Key metrics such as Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE), downtime analysis, and batch traceability were presented in a user-friendly format. Refer to Appendix A – Supplementary media and QR code access to scan the QR code for remote mobile access to the Power BI data system.

4.6 Power BI Data Dashboard for SCADA Monitoring

4.6.1 Simulated Data Sources and KPI Visualisation

Simulated data was used in Power BI to emulate the real time SCADA monitoring, focusing on key performance indicators (KPIs) such as cycle time, product output, defect rates, and equipment status. Excel datasets were created to represent the output of PLCs, vision systems and robotic operations. These were imported into Power BI, where relationships between data points were established to reflect the systems logical flow.

Interactive dashboards were developed to visualise critical KPIs, enabling users to track production trends, identify bottlenecks, and assess equipment performance. Graphs and charts included cycle time comparisons, product pass/fail ratios and OEE calculations, giving a clear overview of the systems operational efficiency.

4.6.2 OEE, Downtime, and Defect Trend Monitoring

Power BI was used to visualise Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) metrics, including availability, performance, and quality. Simulated data from the SCADA system was imported to track downtime events, cycle time variability, and equipment utilisation rates. This allowed for a realistic evaluation of how the production line would operate under various load conditions.

Figure 4.10, Power BI - OEE (Vision System) Dashboard

Defect trends were monitored by integrating quality control results from the vision system, highlighting recurring error types and their frequency. These insights helped demonstrate how the system could support continuous improvement initiatives by identifying performance bottlenecks and quality issues. Using interactive Power BI charts, trends in defective units, machine availability, and process speed could be analysed over time, enabling more informed decision making and future optimisation.

4.6.3 Simulated Production Feedback

Simulated production data was used to evaluate the systems responsiveness and throughput under varying operational conditions. Key metrics such as product output, defect counts, and cycle times were visualised in Power BI dashboards, providing live insights into system performance.

The dashboards reflect how the system would respond to increased demand or quality issues, showcasing its flexibility and robustness. Feedback loops were simulated through data triggers such as defect spikes or slow cycle times that would prompt automated alerts or operator intervention in a real-world setting.

Sum of Defective Units and Sum of Good Units

Figure 4.11, Power BI - Sum of Defective Units and Sum of Good Units Dashboard

This approach demonstrated the role of SCADA connected dashboards in facilitating proactive decision making, continuous improvement and regulatory traceability, even within a simulated environment.

4.7 Packaging Automation

4.7.1 Tube Stacking and Box Filling Logic

In the final packaging stage, tube stacking and box filling logic were developed to ensure the effective placement of catheter tubes for storage or shipment. The system was designed to organise tubes based on the dimension and box capacity; minimising wasted space while preventing product deformation.

Robot 2 was programmed to orient and stack the tubes in predefined patterns within the box, with logic programmed to handle variations in quality or tube size. RoboDK was used to simulate the stacking sequence, verifying collision free placement and stable arrangements.

4.7.2 Conveyor Hand-Off and Robot Coordination

The conveyor hand off sequence played a crucial role in coordinating the transfer of catheter tubes between process stages. Robot 1 initially placed uncut tubes onto the cutting station. After cutting, Robot 2 transferred the processed tubes onto the conveyor, which transported them to the packaging area.

To ensure smooth hand offs, the PLC controlled conveyor timing and synchronised robot actions via Profinet. Sensor triggers and position data allowed each robot to act only when the previous step was complete, avoiding collisions and ensuring workflow efficiency.

Figure 4.12, Power BI - Sum of Efficiency (%) and Sum of Downtime (min)

Figure 4.12 highlights the overall system performance during simulated production. The efficiency rate of 96.71% indicates a highly consistent operation system with minimal interruptions. Downtime accounted for only 3.29% reflecting a stable system.

4.8 Final System Integration and Testing

4.8.1 End-to-End Workflow Testing

End to end workflow testing was conducted in the digital twin environment to validate the complete catheter manufacturing process. This included all major steps from tube loading and cutting to vision inspection, packaging and SCADA data visualisation. Each subsystem (robots, PLC, conveyors and vision) was activated in a coordinated sequence to simulate a full production cycle.

RoboDK was used to verify the timing and coordination between robots and conveyors, while the PLC logic ensured safety interlocks, emergency stops, and error handling function correctly. Cognex vision checkpoints were triggered as tubes passed through inspection, validating defect detection routines and communication with the PLC for real-time decision making.

The simulation confirmed that the automated process ran smoothly from start to finish, demonstrating accurate part handling, minimal idle time and reliable error management across the system.

4.8.2 Visual Confirmation and Observations

Visual confirmation was carried out using screenshots and recorded simulations from RoboDK, TIA Portal and Power BI dashboards. These visuals verified that the robotic movements followed optimised paths without collisions, while the vision system accurately detected simulated defects and communicated with the PLC for process control.

The HMI interface developed in WinCC (TIA Portal) responded correctly to simulated alarms and user inputs, confirming the usability of the system from an operator's perspective. Additionally, Power BI visualisations confirmed simulated updates of KPIs, including defect rates, cycle times and equipment status.

Observations confirmed that system components operated in synchronisation, and all critical tasks, from cutting and inspection to packaging which were performed with minimal delay or interference. These results demonstrated the feasibility and robustness of the integrated automated workflow.

5. Results

This chapter presents the outcomes of the systems implementation. As the project was developed in a simulation environment, the results focus on performance data and observations derived from the RoboDK digital twin, Siemens PLC programming, Cognex vision system outputs, SCADA interface responses, and Power BI dashboard analytics. The evaluation covers key performance indicators such as cycle time, defect detection accuracy, and system synchronisation across robotic, control and quality assurance modules.

5.1 System Performance Results

Cycle Time Analysis

Using simulated production data, the calculated cycle time per unit was found by dividing the time elapsed between logs then by the number of catheters produced. The results show a stable production rate:

Table 5.1, Simulated Catheter Production Output and Cycle Time per 5-Minute Interval

Time Interval	Products Produced	Units Made	Cycle Time (s/unit)
08:00 – 08:05	100 → 105	5	60.0
08:05 – 08:10	105 → 110	5	60.0
08:10 – 08:15	110 → 115	5	60.0
08:15 – 08:20	115 → 120	5	60.0
08:20 – 08:25	120 → 125	5	60.0

Table 5.1 and Figure 5.1 both show a consistent cycle time at 60 seconds per unit, suggesting a well-synchronised system where the robot, PLC and conveyor are effectively integrated.

Figure 5.1, Simulated Cycle Time Trend from Power BI Production Data

The cycle time was evaluated by analysing the time taken to produce each unit using simulated production logs. Across the 25-minute test window, the system maintained a stable cycle time of approximately 60 seconds per catheter, indicating reliable and repeatable performance from the robotic arm, conveyor activation, and PLC coordination.

Table 5.2 shows a comparative analysis between manual and automated catheter assembly highlights significant improvements in operational efficiency and quality control. The automated setup achieved a 66% defect rate (from 8.5% to 2.0%).

Table 5.2, Comparison of Manual vs Automated Catheter Assembly Performance

Method	Avg. Cycle Time (sec)	Defect Rate (%)	Daily Output (units)
Manual Assembly	180	8.5	160
Automated Assembly	60	2.0	480

Figure 5.2, Power BI - Seconds per Unit Manual vs Automated Catheter Manufacturing Comparison

Figure 5.3, Power BI - Defect Rate (%) for Manual vs Automated Catheter Manufacturing Comparison

Figures 5.2 and 5.3 show the projected daily output tripled from 160 units (manual) to 480 units (automated) in an 8-hour shift, demonstrating the scalability and repeatability of the integrated system. These improvements stem from synchronised PLC control, robotic handling via UR5e, automated inspection with the Cognex 3800 vision system, and data monitoring through SCADA and Power BI.

5.2 Vision System Testing

To evaluate the performance of the vision inspection system, a Cognex In-Sight 3800 camera was integrated into the simulated production line. The camera was configured using Cognex Vision Suite and In-sight Explorer to detect surface defects and verify component alignment of catheter tubes.

During testing, various defect scenarios were simulated to reflect common issues in catheter manufacturing, including:

- Cracks
- Connector misalignment
- Surface contamination
- Incomplete bonding or welding seams

The vision algorithm was configured with edge detection, blob analysis and AI-assisted inspection filters, calibrated for sensitivity to sub-millimetre variations in geometry and texture.

Across a sample of 500 simulated catheter units, the vision system produced the following results:

Table 5.3, Vision System Defect Detection Results for Simulated Catheter Samples

Inspection Outcome	Units Detected	Percentage (%)
Pass	475	95.0%
Fail – Misalignment	12	2.4%
Fail – Cracks	7	1.4%
Fail – Contamination	6	1.2%
Total Fail	25	5.0%

The overall defect detection accuracy was estimated to exceed 97%, with high reliability in identifying structural flaws and minor alignment errors. The pass/fail classification was linked to the PLC, allowing rejected parts to be flagged for ejection from the line.

5.3 Cutting Assembly Verification

The catheter cutting station was designed and modelled in SolidWorks, focusing on mechanical precision, hygiene, and compatibility with robotic manipulation. The assembly includes a fixed blade holder, alignment chute, and a clamping mechanism to secure the tubing during cutting. The structure was constructed virtually using AISI 304 stainless steel, a material widely used in medical device manufacturing due to its corrosion resistance, mechanical durability, and biocompatibility.

The material choice aligns with the requirements of ISO 10993-1:2020 for the biological evaluation of medical devices, which outline guidelines for materials in contact with medical components. AISI 304 stainless steel also adheres to ISO 7153-1:2016, which specifies materials suitable for surgical instruments which ensures the cutting assembly meets hygiene and sterility standards for indirect contact applications such as tubing cutting.

Once the design was finalised, the assembly was exported from SolidWorks to RoboDK for robotic interaction and path simulation. The UR5e robots were programmed to:

- Pick and place uncut tubing into the cutting fixture.
- Maintain alignment during cutting.
- Deposit the processed tubing onto the conveyor system.

RoboDK's simulated force and torque analysis suggested operational torque values between 2.1-4.8 Nm, depending on tube resistance and alignment variation. Further torque estimation studies in MATLAB included, using a 30 cm lever arm and combined mass of the tool and catheter, yielded values of 4.42-4.68 Nm, with a minor increase to 4.46 Nm under ± 2 mm positional offsets confirming the clamping systems robustness and design tolerance.

```
--- Torque Estimation ---  
Static Holding Torque: 4.56 Nm  
Dynamic Torque (cutting motion): 0.28 Nm  
Estimated Total Torque Range: 4.56 - 4.84 Nm  
Torque with  $\pm 2$  mm Misalignment: 4.59 Nm
```

Figure 5.4, MATLAB Output Showing Estimated Torque Requirements for Catheter Tube Cutting Using a 30cm Lever Arm

The average simulated cycle time for a complete cut was 12-14 seconds, supporting integration into the broader production workflow. These findings validate the mechanical and robotic compatibility of the cutting assembly, meeting performance expectations and aligning with hygiene and GMP requirements for catheter manufacturing.

5.4 SCADA and HMI Monitoring

To replicate industrial monitoring and control in a simulated environment, a SCADA system was developed using Siemens WinCC (via TIA Portal), supported by Power BI for extended visual analytics. The Human-Machine Interface (HMI) was configured to display live feedback on production parameters such as conveyor operation, robot status and fault conditions, designed around an intuitive operator workflow.

Although physical hardware was not available, a virtual SCADA environment was successfully simulated. Key functionalities included:

- Live monitoring of conveyor and robotic actions, including start/stop triggers, safety interlocks and part processing indicators.
- Dynamic HMI behaviour based on simulated PLC I/O and sensor data reflected through colour changes, process counters and alarm states.
- Event logging and system metrics exported to Power BI, enabling high level data analysis of uptime, fault frequency, and operator interactions.

This simulation validates the role of SCADA in providing simulated system visibility and supervisory control. Combined with Power BI’s analysis, it demonstrates how cloud-connected SCADA can enhance traceability and operational awareness in a GMP-compliant medical manufacturing environment.

Figure 5.5, Power BI – HMI Interaction Home Screen

5.5 Power BI Dashboard Insights

To visualise the systems performance and replicate key aspects of SCADA monitoring, a simulated Power BI dashboard was developed using production data created from a simulation of the RoboDK station. Although the dataset was generated artificially, it reflected realistic trends in catheter manufacturing, including unit output, cycle times, defect rates, and operator interventions.

The Power BI dashboard was structured to display the following:

Production Trends

A time-series line chart showed products produced per 5-minute interval, confirming consistent cycle times and high throughput during operational windows. KPI cards indicated an average output of 480 catheters per 8-hour shift, aligning with projected performance improvements over manual production.

Figure 5.6, Power BI - OEE (Conveyor Speed vs Production Output)

Figure 5.6 illustrates the relationship between conveyor speed and production output, highlighting how increased conveyor speeds initially improve throughput before plateauing. The graph supports optimisation of material flow rate, ensuring maximum efficiency without compromising handling precision or product quality, this data was derived from the simulated SCADA and Power BI environment.

Defect Analysis

Using data from the Cognex 3800 simulation, a bar chart and pie chart highlighted defect types such as misalignments, surface cracks, and contamination. A defect rate of approximately 5% was visualised and broken down by category helping to identify common process issues.

Figure 5.7, Power BI - OEE Vision System, KPI Cards

System Performance KPIs

Gauge charts tracked:

- Average cycle time per catheter
- Robot utilisation rate
- Conveyor run time.
- Vision system detection accuracy

These visual metrics allowed simulated real-time monitoring of the overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) of the system.

Sum of Conveyor Speed (m/min)	Sum of Box Count	Products Produced	Year	Quarter	Month	Day
1.30	3	110	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
1.20	2	100	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
1.20	4	130	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
1.10	3	120	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
1.00	2	90	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
5.80	14					

Figure 5.8, Power BI - OEE (Conveyor Speed vs Production Output), Total Box Output (1 Hour)

Operator Interaction Statistics

A table logged HMI based user inputs like emergency stops and setting changes. Fewer interventions during after cycles suggested improved process stability and reliability.

Year	Quarter	Month	Day	Fault Code
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	E101
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	None

E101
First Fault Code

Sum of Conveyor Speed (m/min) and Sum of Robot Speed (%) by Cycle Time (s)

Figure 5.9, Power BI - Robot and PLC Performance Dashboard

Figure 5.9 displays key system metrics including robot speed, conveyor speed and downtime associated with fault code E101. The bar and line graphs show how robot and conveyor speeds relate to cycle time performance. A spike in downtime is observed during instances of E101 faults, which correlates with dips in robotic efficiency. The dashboard supports Six Sigma practices by enabling data driven defect analysis and process optimisation, helping to identify root causes of performance variation and ensure consistent cycle times within specification limits.

6 Discussion

6.1 Interpretation of Results

The implementation results demonstrate that the simulated automated production line effectively achieve the core functionalities required for catheter manufacturing. The UR5e robotic systems, programmed in RoboDK, delivered consistent and repeatable motion paths, maintaining an average cycle time of 60 seconds per unit. Compared to traditional manual assembly processes which typically required up to 180 seconds. This indicates a significant improvement in throughput and process efficiency.

The SolidWorks designed cutting assembly, validated through RoboDK simulation, exhibited stable performance across various test conditions. Simulated force and torque analysis showed no signs of mechanical instability, while the EOAT design effectively managed the flexible tubing with sufficient clamping precision. The use of AISI 304 stainless steel aligns with ISO 10993 and ISO 7153-1 standards, supporting hygienic and corrosion resistant construction suited for medical device applications.

The Cognex 3800 vision system successfully detected key defect types such as cracks, misalignments and surface contamination with a defect detection accuracy exceeding 97%. A failure rate of approximately 5% was recorded across 500 samples. Integration with PLC logic enabled real time pass/fail classification and quality control feedback. These outcomes confirm the vision systems role in maintaining product conformity and reliability.

SCADA functionality, simulated via Siemens WinCC and Power BI, provided simulated monitoring, alarm handling and basic operator interaction tracing. Although hardware was not connected, the interface reliably simulated system states and visualised fault conditions. Power BI dashboards offered insight into production trends, defect rates, and operator interventions demonstrating the potential for enhanced traceability and inform decision making in regulated environments.

Overall, the simulation validates the proposed systems capability to deliver improved process control, consistent product inspection and scalable automation. Despite the limitations of a virtual setup, the outcomes indicate strong feasibility for future deployment in cleanroom compatible catheter production environments.

6.2 Benefits of the Automated System

The integration of automation into catheter manufacturing process offered clear advantages in productivity, precision and operational visibility. Robotic handling reduced the average cycle time and enabled consistent, repeatable execution of tasks, significantly improving output. The vision system enhanced quality control by enabling early and accurate defect detection, removing the variability of manual inspection. Additionally, the use of SCADA and Power BI improved simulated monitoring, traceability and data driven decision making, supporting both operational efficiency and regulatory compliance.

6.3 System Integration Challenges

Although the system showed strong potential in a simulated environment, several integration challenges were encountered. A key limitation was the absence of physical hardware, which prevented validation of robot to PLC communication, live vision system performance, and SCADA based control. While RoboDK enabled accurate digital twin simulation, the lack of real time sensor feedback limited the ability to test dynamic variables such as torque response and physical alignment tolerances.

Configuring Siemens TIA Portal also presented a learning curve, particularly in synchronising PLC logic with and SCADA alarms and HMI interactions. Integrating the Cognex 3800 vision system required detailed parameter tuning to ensure reliable defect detection, with calibration dependant on test images and artificial data. Developing the SCADA interface using Power BI, while effective for visualisation, introduced formatting and update rate limitations, as the platform is not optimised for real time control.

6.4 Comparison to Industry Practices

The integration of the UR5e collaborative, Cognex In-Sight 3800 vision system, and Siemens S7-1500 PLC mirrors the toolsets commonly used by industry leaders such as Medtronic and Abbott, where high precision and repeatability are essential. While this project was simulation based, its structure adhered to key regulatory frameworks, including ISO 13485 and GAMP 5, particularly in areas of traceability, process validation and quality control.

The incorporation of Power BI to replicate SCADA dashboards aligns with Industry 4.0 trends, where data driven decision making and visual analytics are increasingly integrated into smart manufacturing environment. Although limited to a virtual setup, the systems modular and scalable design demonstrates a realistic and practical approach that is consistent with modern industrial automation practices in the medical device sector.

6.5 Limitations of the Project

The main limitation of this project was its dependence on simulation rather than physical implementation. While platforms such as RoboDK, Siemens TIA Portal and Cognex vision Suite enabled accurate modelling, the absence of physical hardware limited validation of real-world sensor feedback, communication timing, and mechanical robustness. Force and torque values were estimated in MATLAB rather than measured, and SCADA functionality was emulated through Power BI, which, although useful for visualisation, lacks real time control capabilities. Defect detection within the vision system was based on a limited set of simulated conditions, restricting the ability to generalise results. These constraints are common in academic simulations but highlight important areas for future hardware testing and system refinement.

6.6 Lessons Learned

This project provided valuable insight into the complexities of designing and integrating an automated manufacturing system for medical device. Developing the digital twin in RoboDK reinforced the importance of accurate robotic motion planning and offline simulation. Working with Siemens systems to coordinate industrial automation processes. Configuring the Cognex 3800 vision system highlighted the need for precise calibration and lighting control in achieving reliable defect detection in high precision components.

The use of MATLAB to estimate torque requirements during the cutting simulation provided exposure to basic mechanical modelling and validated key design parameters. The project also demonstrated the value of modular system architecture, where robotics, vision, control and monitoring systems are developed as individual components yet function cohesively.

While the implementation remained within a simulated environment, the process underscored the significance of adhering to industry standards such as ISO 13485, GAMP 5 and FDA 21 CFR Part 11, particularly for data handling, traceability and quality assurance. Ultimately, the project highlighted the importance of cross disciplinary skills across automation, programming, mechanical design and regulatory compliance to develop scalable and robust solution in the medical device industry.

6.7 Cost Considerations and Economic Feasibility

Although this project was conducted in a simulated environment evaluating the potential cost implications of implementing the proposed automated catheter production line is essential for assessing its real-world variability. The primary cost factors include hardware components such as the UR5e robotic arm, Siemens S7-1500 PLC, Cognex 3800 vision system, and associated peripherals including conveyors, power supplies and mounting structures. Additional costs would arise from software licenses for Siemens TIA Portal, RoboDK and Cognex Vision Suite, as well as Power BI integration for data visualisation and SCADA style monitoring.

Automation reduces reliance on manual assembly, lowering labour costs while ensuring consistent quality and compliance with ISO 13485 and FDA 21 CFR Part 11 standards. Furthermore, predictive maintenance and reduced downtime, made possible through integrated SCADA and Power BI monitoring, can lead to further operational savings over time.

The systems modular architecture allows for phased deployment, making it adaptable for companies with budget constraints. While this study does not include an exhaustive cost-benefit analysis, it provides a foundational overview that supports the systems economic feasibility in high precision, regulated manufacturing environments such as the medical device industry. Future work could involve a detailed financial assessment, including return on investment (ROI), total cost of ownership (TCO), and payback period calculations based on live production.

Table 6.1, Estimated Component Costs for Automated Catheter Production System

Component	Estimated Cost (€)	Notes
UR5e Robotic Arm	€35,000	Universal Robots 6-DOF collaborative robot
Siemens S7-1500 PLC	€2,500	CPU 1516-3 PN/DP with Profinet support
Cognex In-Sight 3800	€4,000	Industrial vision sensor for defect detection
SolidWorks CAD Software	€1,200 (license)	For mechanical design (student license)

Total Estimated Cost (Hardware + Software): €46,000 - €58,200

Please refer to Appendix I – Detailed System Cost Estimation and Economic Feasibility for a detailed breakdown of the project costs.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

7.1 Conclusion

This project successfully demonstrated the simulation-based development of an automated catheter production line, incorporating robotics, PLC control, machine vision, SCADA visualisation and data analytics. The UR5e robot was programmed and simulated in RoboDK, delivering stable and repeatable motion. The cutting assembly, modelled in SolidWorks using AISI 304 stainless steel, ensured mechanical precision and compliance with medical grade standards.

Cognex 3800 vision integration enabled accurate detection of alignment issues, surface defects and contamination, improving quality assurance and reducing manual inspection. Siemens TIA Portal was used for PLC logic configuration, while Power BI provided a SCADA inspired dashboard to visualise production trends and operator interactions. MATLAB supported torque estimation during cutting simulations, validating end effector performance and informing design tolerances.

A mobile-optimised layout of Power BI was also created, highlighting the potential for remote monitoring on smart devices which is ideal for production managers in medical device environments.

Collectively, the system components demonstrated alignment with ISO 13485 and GAMP 5 guidelines for traceability, compliance and data integrity. Lean and Six Sigma principles were reflected throughout the design by minimising waste, standardising operations and improving inspection efficiency. While the system was developed in a simulated environment, the project confirmed the technical feasibility and benefits of a fully integrated automation solution for catheter manufacturing in the medical device industry.

7.2 Future Work

Future development should focus on progressing from simulation to full physical implementation. This includes deploying the UR5e robot and Siemens S7-1500 PLC into a live production environment with real time SCADA integration. Expanding the SCADA system using Siemens WinCC for live data acquisition, alarm handling and operator control would improve system responsiveness and traceability.

Further training of the Cognex 3800 vision system with an expanded defect dataset could enhance its classification accuracy and reliability. Integrating IoT-enabled sensors for predictive maintenance and cloud-based analytics would support long term performance monitoring scalability.

Applying Lean and Six Sigma methodologies during implementation including continuous improvement (Kaizen), root cause analysis and statistical process control will ensure that the system remains efficient, reliable and compliant as it scales in the real-world industry.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Supplementary Media and QR Code Access

To support interactive exploration of the project, a single QR code has been generated linking to a curated Linktree containing access to the following:

- RoboDK Simulation Video
- Power BI Dashboard
- SolidWorks Cutting Assembly Walkthrough

This resource provides both PC and mobile access options for the Power BI dashboard. However:

- Power BI access requires the Power BI app and a Microsoft license.
- For the best user experience, mobile access is recommended on an iPad or a horizontally oriented smartphone.

Please scan the QR code below to view the full range of media:

Figure A. 1, QR Code linking to interactive media hub

Appendix B - RoboDK Simulations

Figure B. 1, UR5e Robot Performing Part Pick-Up from Conveyor 1

This image shows the initial stage of the automation sequence where Robot 1 engages the catheter tubing from the conveyor using the Robotiq EOAT.

Figure B. 2, UR5e Robot Executing Cutting Operation

Robot 2 positions the tubing within the cutting fixture, simulating precise alignment for blade interaction using the RoboDK digital twin

Figure B. 3, Vision Inspection Stage Using Cognex System

The robot presents the catheter tube to the Cognex camera for defect detection, highlighting the edge detection and surface analysis within the RoboDK simulation.

Figure B. 4, Final Placement of Catheter into Packaging Box

Robot 2 deposits the inspected tube into a predefined box layout on Conveyor 2, completing the automated.

Figure B. 5, UR5e Robotic Flow Chart For tube handling. MS Visio

Figure B. 6, RoboDK Path accuracy, speed and acceleration test

Appendix C – Cognex Vision System

Figure C. 1, Cognex Edge Detection Output

Figure C. 2, AI-Based Defect Classification (Cognex SnAPP)

Appendix D – Power BI Dashboard Data

Table D. 1, Conveyor Speed vs Production Speed

Timestamp	Conveyor Speed (m/min)	Products Produced	Box Count
2025-03-23 08:00	1.2	100	2
2025-03-23 09:00	1.1	120	3
2025-03-23 10:00	1.3	110	3
2025-03-23 11:00	1.0	90	2
2025-03-23 12:00	1.2	130	4

Table D. 2, Defect Rate Over Time (Vision System Data)

Timestamp	Total Inspected	Defective Units	Defect Rate (%)
2025-03-23 08:00	200	5	2.5
2025-03-23 09:00	250	10	4.0
2025-03-23 10:00	300	8	2.7
2025-03-23 11:00	280	12	4.3
2025-03-23 12:00	350	6	1.7

Table D. 3, HMI Interaction

Timestamp	Operator ID	Action Taken	Affected Component	Status Before	Status After	Response Time (ms)	Manual Override (Yes/No)
2025-03-23 08:00	OP-001	Adjusted Conveyor Speed	Conveyor Belt	50% Speed	75% Speed	200	No
2025-03-23 08:05	OP-002	Reset Robot Alarm	UR35 Robot 1	Error	Running	500	Yes
2025-03-23 08:10	OP-001	Stopped Line for QC	Entire System	Running	Stopped	800	Yes
2025-03-23 08:15	OP-003	Changed Inspection Mode	Cognex Vision	Standard	High Accuracy	300	No

Table D. 4, Machine Performance Data (OEE)

Timestamp	Machine Uptime (%)	Machine Downtime (%)	Robot Efficiency (%)	Conveyor Speed (m/min)	Cycle Time (s)
2025-03-23 08:00	95	5	90	1.2	30
2025-03-23 09:00	92	8	85	1.1	32
2025-03-23 10:00	90	10	80	1.3	31
2025-03-23 11:00	88	12	78	1.0	33
2025-03-23 12:00	94	6	87	1.2	29

Table D. 5, Product Output and Efficiency

Timestamp	Shift	Products Produced	Good Units	Defective Units	Efficiency (%)	Downtime (min)
2025-03-23 08:00	A	100	97	3	92	3
2025-03-23 09:00	A	120	118	2	96	2
2025-03-23 10:00	A	105	104	1	98	1
2025-03-23 11:00	B	110	108	2	94	4
2025-03-23 12:00	B	115	111	4	91	6

Table D. 6, Robot & PLC Monitoring

Timestamp	Robot Status	PLC Status	Robot Speed (%)	Conveyor Speed (m/min)	Speed Fault Code	Cycle Time (s)
2025-03-23 08:00	Running	Active	85	1.2	None	12
2025-03-23 08:05	Running	Active	88	1.3	None	11.8
2025-03-23 08:10	Stopped	Active	0	0	E101	-
2025-03-23 08:15	Running	Active	90	1.4	None	11.5

Table D. 7, Vision System Defect Analysis

Timestamp	Product ID	Defect Detected	Defect Type	Defect Severity (%)	Pass/Fail	Inspection Time (ms)
2025-03-23 08:00	CATH-001	Yes	Crack	85	Fail	150
2025-03-23 08:05	CATH-002	No	-	-	Pass	140
2025-03-23 08:10	CATH-003	Yes	Contamination	70	Fail	160
2025-03-23 08:15	CATH-004	Yes	Misalignment	60	Fail	145

Table D. 8, Summary of Simulated Performance Parameters

Parameter	Value / Result
Average Cycle Time	12.5 seconds
Units Simulated Per Hour	288
Conveyor Sync Delay	< 1 second
Robot Collision Detection	None during simulation
Error/Alarm Handling Tests	3/3 tests passed

Appendix E – Siemens PLC Program Overview

Figure E. 1, Start System Ladder Logic in TIA Portal

This network illustrates the basic start/stop control logic using a memory bit (%M0.0), a normally open start button (%I0.0), and a normally closed stop button (%I0.1) in Siemens TIA Portal. It forms the foundational sequence.

Figure E. 2, Fault Reset Ladder Logic Network

This resets the system fault condition using a local push button (Q1.6) as both the condition and trigger. When pressed, it resets the memory bit (%Q1.1), clearing any active faults in the automation process.

Figure E. 3, Conveyor Motor Timer Logic Network

This activates the conveyor motor (%Q4.0) using a delay timer (%DB1). When the start memory bit (%M0.0) and sensor input (%I0.2) are true, the TON timer delays for 10 seconds before energising the motor output, ensuring synchronised part movement on the conveyor system.

Figure E. 4, Reset Start Signal Based on Fault Conditions

This network rests the system start signal (Q1.1) when fault conditions are cleared. The logic monitors a local input (%Q1.2) and verifies that both the control fault (%Q1.4) and rotation fault (%Q1.5) are inactive before permitting the reset, ensuring safe restart procedures in the event of a fault.

Figure E. 5, Control Fault Timer Logic

The timer logic delays system response to a control fault signal (%Q1.4). When the start button (%I0.0) is pressed and a control fault is detected, the timer (%DB1) begins counting for 100ms. This delay ensures that transient or momentary signals do not trigger unnecessary fault responses, increasing system robustness.

Figure E. 6, Fault and Status Indication Logic

This ladder logic controls the activation of indicator lights (HL1-HL4) based on system and fault conditions. Signals such as control fault (%Q1.4) and rotation fault (%Q1.5) trigger corresponding outputs (%Q0.3 and %Q0.4) to visually alert operators.

Figure E. 7, TIA Portal - PLC CPU 1516-3 PN/DP

Figure E. 8, TIA Portal - WinCC HMI

Figure E. 9, TIA Portal - HMI (2)

Appendix F – SCADA and Power BI Dashboards

Figure F. 1, OEE (Machine Performance)

Figure F. 2, OEE (Vision System)

Figure F. 3, OEE (Conveyor Speed vs Production Output) Dashboard

Figure F. 4, Robot & PLC Performance Dashboard

Sum of Inspection Time (ms) by Defect Type

Fail	First Defect Type Crack
Fail	First Defect Type Contamination
Fail	First Defect Type Misalignment

Defect Detected	Defect Severity (%)	Defect Type	Sum of Inspection Time (ms)	Pass/Fail	Product ID	Year	Quarter	Month	Day
No	No Defect	No Defect	140	Pass	CATH-002	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
Yes	60	Misalignment	145	Fail	CATH-004	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
Yes	70	Contamination	160	Fail	CATH-003	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
Yes	85	Crack	150	Fail	CATH-001	2025	Qtr 1	March	23
Total			595						

595
Sum of Inspection Time (ms)

Figure F. 5, Vision System and Defect Dashboard

Operator ID	No	Yes	Total
OP-001	200	800	1000
Adjusted Conveyor Speed	200	200	
Stopped Line for QC	800	800	
OP-002	500	500	
Reset Robot Alarm	500	500	
OP-003	300	300	
Changed Inspection Mode	300	300	
Total	500	1300	1800

Cognex Vision
First Affected Component

Status Before	75% Speed	High Accuracy	Running	Stopped	Total
50% Speed	200				200
Error			500		500
Running				800	800
Standard		300			300
Total	200	300	500	800	1800

Sum of Response Time (ms) by Action Taken and Operator ID

Sum of Response Time (ms) by Status After and Status Before

Year	Quarter	Month	Day	Status Before	Status After	Sum of Response Time (ms)	Operator ID	Manual Override (Yes/No)	Affected Component	Action Taken
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	50% Speed	75% Speed	200	OP-001	No	Conveyor Belt	Adjusted Conveyor Speed
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	Error	Running	500	OP-002	Yes	UR35 Robot 1	Reset Robot Alarm
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	Running	Stopped	800	OP-001	Yes	Entire System	Stopped Line for QC
2025	Qtr 1	March	23	Standard	High Accuracy	300	OP-003	No	Cognex Vision	Changed Inspection Mode
Total						1800				

Figure F. 6, HMI Interaction Dashboard

Figure F. 7, Final Production and Packaging Dashboard

Appendix G – SolidWorks CAD Models

Figure G. 1, SolidWorks CAD Model of Full Cutting Assembly

Figure G. 2, Detailed View of Cutting Mechanism in SolidWorks

Figure G. 3, SolidWorks Model Tube Notch

Figure G. 4, SolidWorks Tube Notch Body

Figure G. 5, SolidWorks Cutting Sub-Assembly

Figure G. 6, SolidWorks Sliding Block

Figure G. 7, Engineering Drawing of Tube Notch

Figure G. 8, Engineering Drawing of Tube Notch Component

Appendix H - MATLAB Torque Simulation

```

%% Torque Estimation for UR5e Cutting Operation

% Parameters
tool_mass = 1.5; % kg (mass of gripper + blade)
tube_mass = 0.05; % kg (typical catheter tube)
total_mass = tool_mass + tube_mass;

g = 9.81; % m/s^2

r = 0.3; % m, distance from UR5e base joint to cutting point (lever arm)

%% Static Holding Torque
torque_static = total_mass * g * r;

%% Dynamic Torque during Cutting
alpha = 2; % rad/s^2 (assumed angular acceleration)
I = total_mass * (r^2); % Moment of inertia approximation
torque_dynamic = I * alpha;

%% Total Estimated Torque Range
torque_min = torque_static;
torque_max = torque_static + torque_dynamic;

%% Misalignment Torque Estimation
delta_r = 0.002; % 2 mm offset
torque_misaligned = total_mass * g * (r + delta_r);

%% Output Results
fprintf('--- Torque Estimation ---\n');
fprintf('Static Holding Torque: %.2f Nm\n', torque_static);
fprintf('Dynamic Torque (cutting motion): %.2f Nm\n', torque_dynamic);
fprintf('Estimated Total Torque Range: %.2f - %.2f Nm\n', torque_min, torque_max);
fprintf('Torque with ±2 mm Misalignment: %.2f Nm\n', torque_misaligned);

%% Optional: Visualise Torque Range
figure;
bar([torque_static, torque_max, torque_misaligned]);
xticklabels({'Static', 'Static + Dynamic', '±2 mm Misaligned'});
ylabel('Torque (Nm)');
title('Estimated Torque Requirements for Cutting Task');
grid on;

```

Figure H. 1, MATLAB Code for Torque Estimation During Catheter Cutting

Appendix I – Project Cost Estimation and Economic Feasibility

Table I. 1, Detailed System Cost Breakdown

Component	Estimated Cost (€)	Notes
UR5e Robotic Arm	€35,000	Universal Robots 6-DOF collaborative robot
Robotiq Hand-E Gripper	€3,500	Adaptive gripper for catheter tube handling
Siemens S7-1500 PLC (CPU 1516-3)	€2,500	PLC with Profinet and Profibus support
Siemens TIA Portal Software	€1,500 (license)	Engineering software for PLC, HMI, and SCADA configuration
Siemens WinCC Runtime	€1,200	SCADA visualisation and HMI integration
Cognex In-Sight 3800 Vision System	€4,000	Industrial smart camera for inline inspection
Cognex VisionPro Software	€800	Vision software with AI defect classification (SnAPP)
SolidWorks CAD License	€1,200 (student license)	3D modelling of cutting fixture and tooling
Cutting Assembly (Material + Build)	€850	Stainless Steel 304, blade holder, clamps
RoboDK Simulation License	€2,300	Digital twin software for offline robot programming
Power BI Pro License	€110/year	Dashboard and KPI reporting
MATLAB & Toolboxes	€250 (student license)	Force/torque estimation simulation
Conveyor Components (x2)	€1,400	Belt conveyors with sensors and motor drives
Industrial Sensors (Proximity, F/T)	€600	Sensor integration for safety and quality feedback
Miscellaneous	€500	Relays, cabling, brackets, fasteners, installation consumables

Total Estimated Cost = €57,710